

Heterostructured core-shell metal oxide-based nanobrushes for ultrafast UV photodetectors

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ABSTRACT

Ultrafast UV photodetectors (UV PDs) are crucial components in modern optoelectronics because conventional detectors have reached a bottleneck with low integration, functionalities, and efficiency. Core-shell metal oxide nanobrushes (MOx NBs)-based UV PDs have enhanced the absorption, tunable performance, and good compatibility for diversified applications, including imaging, self-powered systems, remote communications, security, and wearable electronics. Core-shell PDs are developed with complex hierarchical or heterostructured configurations that encapsulate 1D MOx nanowires on 1D nanostructures (NSs) to transport high charge carrier mobility or efficiency by reducing scattering and recombination rates. This review presents a thorough development of MOx core-shell microstructure for the enhancement of detection response and stability with controlled parameters for multifunctional applications. Significant roles of MOx NBs-based UV PDs exploring various growth techniques and complex photodetection mechanisms with their challenges, limitations, and prospects, providing valuable insights for propelling the progression of photodetector technology in this comprehensive review are discussed meticulously. The novelty of MOx NBs-based UV PDs lies in their distinctive brush-like morphology aspect, tunable properties, and improved performance compared to other NSs, for rapid and sensitive response ($\sim\mu\text{s}$ -ms) under UV light illumination. The diverse photoresponse parameters and multifunctional applications of UV PDs incorporating MOx NBs are carefully summarized, which will set the roadmap for future photodetector technology.

1. UV photodetectors: metal oxide nanobrushes

UV photodetectors (UV PDs) are highly functional devices that can detect and quantify ultraviolet light [1–7] for diverse industries, including photovoltaic energy generation, health monitoring, scientific research, environmental studies, and technological advancements [8–10]. For instance, UV PDs are utilized in wearable electronic devices such as smartwatches and fitness trackers to provide real-time information about UV exposure, enabling individuals to make informed decisions about sun protection [11–13]. To understand and mitigate potential environmental effects, UV PDs also contribute significantly to

environmental monitoring by detecting the amount of UV radiation in the atmosphere and providing data on atmospheric conditions, such as ozone concentrations [14,15]. UV PDs are critical components in security systems [16] that receive and decode secure UV signals in military applications, as UV signal communication is more advanced than traditional radiofrequency communication [17]. UV PDs are used to receive and interpret UV signals in space-based communication systems, where standard radiofrequency signals may face challenges [18].

Additionally, UV PDs are essential tools in the photovoltaic energy generation industry [19], contributing to the development, testing, and optimization of solar cells and systems [20,21]. UV PDs are employed in

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solar cells to measure spectral response, monitor standard quality control purposes, quantify UV-induced degradation, and identify faults, cracks, or irregularities [22,23]. Overall, UV PDs are versatile and essential instruments that accurately measure and detect UV radiation, enabling various practical and beneficial applications (Fig. 1). The increased demand for sophisticated and efficient UV PDs with exceptional sensitivity and object recognition capabilities has led researchers and scientists to develop advanced PDs to improve the performance, efficiency, and durability of solar energy technologies.

Three-dimensional (3D) heterostructured metal oxide (MOx) nanostructures (NSs) [24] can significantly improve the physical and chemical properties of nanoscale advanced UV PDs [25,26]. These NSs possess a high surface-to-volume ratio and flexibility, enabling fast response, easy integration, and efficient device utilization to achieve high sensitivity, signal-to-noise ratio, speed, spectral selectivity, and stability [27,28]. Mishra et al. synthesized ZnO-tetrapods using a simple flame transport synthesis (FTS) method and utilized them for UV detection [29]. Under UV light illumination, there is a 90 % increase in current ($I_{uvon}/I_{uvoff} \sim 28-584$, $d = 1-0.1$ mm) and a relatively quick responsive time compared to 1D NSs [30]. Gedamu et al. synthesized networked ZnO nanoneedles and nanotetrapods using flame

transport-based techniques (B-FTS and C-FTS) and investigated the photoconduction mechanism. At UV illumination (365 nm), the reported on/off ratio is $312-4.5 \times 10^3$ and the response time is 22-67 ms under 0.3-2.4 V bias voltage [31]. Despite the promising photo-detecting parameters exhibited by the 3D Heterostructured MOx-based UV PDs, their performance is affected by certain drawbacks, such as low photocurrent, flexibility, thermal stability, and slow response/recovery time caused by defect traps [32,33]. The increased detecting performance of these UV PDs can be achieved by confining the 1D NSs, which is done by encapsulating and then branching the NSs. This results in the growth of brush-like nanoheterostructure or Nano Brushes (NBs), exhibiting a high surface-to-volume ratio and has the potential for UV PDs, which are further characterized in photoconductive and photoemissive PDs because of their minimal dimensional NSs quantum impact [34].

For diversified applications, several wide bandgap III-V compound semiconductors, gallium nitride (GaN) [35], silicon carbide (SiC), aluminum arsenide (AlAs), aluminum phosphide (AlP), and boron nitride (BN) are explored for the practical functionalization of UV PDs [36]. Kaushik et al. produced plasmonic-enhanced deep-UV PDs based on hexagonal-BN (h-BN) nanosheets. At UV illumination, a 5.5 times

Fig. 1. UV PDs based devices, their applications and methods for the development of nanobrushes.

increase in current and ~60 % responsivity is reported at a low input voltage of 1 V [37]. Kwak et al. prepared ⁰D-²D hybrid optoelectronic devices using nontoxic InP quantum dots (QDs) demonstrating high sensitivity and high performance due to the high absorption coefficient of 0D materials with a tunable detection range and a high carrier transport property of 0D materials. The InP QDs hybrid PDs demonstrate a high responsivity of 1×10^9 A/W and detectivity of 4.5×10^{16} Jones at $0.05 \mu\text{Wcm}^{-2}$ under 405 nm illumination [38]. Although most efforts concentrate on wide bandgap III-V compound semiconductors-based UV PDs, these PDs have drawbacks, including high production costs and incompatibilities with current technology [39]. Also, the complexity of processing wide bandgap III-V compound semiconductors may require specialized equipment, which hinders widespread acceptance and economic feasibility and limits the viability of vast bandgap III-V compound semiconductors-based UV PDs [4,40]. Despite the promising photo-detecting parameters exhibited by the MOx array-based UV PDs, their

performance is affected by certain drawbacks, such as low photocurrent and high response/recovery time caused by defect traps. Dai et al. fabricated Ag/ZnO-microrod/Ag UV PDs showing a hexagonal whispering gallery cavity. The manufactured device offers a fast response time, $\tau_r = 6.28$ sec, a high sensitivity of 4×10^4 A/W and a high photocurrent gain of 1.5×10^5 at 5 V bias [32]. The increased detecting performance of these UV PDs can be achieved by confining the 1D NSs, which is done by encapsulating and then branching the NSs. This results in the growth of brush-like nanoheterostructure or NBs, exhibiting a high surface-to-volume ratio and has the potential for UV PDs devices, which are further characterized in photoconductive and photoemissive PDs because of their minimal dimensional NSs quantum impact.

Despite the extensive studies of III-V semiconductors, the wide bandgap metal oxide (MOx) semiconductors (ZnO, Cu₂O, SnO₂, and TiO₂) have also been extensively used for the fabrication of UV PDs in the practical world [29,41–43]. MOx semiconductors can exhibit unique

Fig. 2. (a) Schematic structure of the MOx NBs-based UV PDs along with its SEM images, Performance aspects and their In-field Applications; (b) The bar chart represents (i) the number of published articles on PDs and UV PDs from 1990 to 2023 and (ii) the number of articles published on MOx-based UV PDs concerning different MOx. Data was collected from the Web of Science.

characteristics, such as high excitonic binding energy, large bandgap, exceptional thermal and environmental stabilities, and good optical properties [44–46]. MOx-based UV photodetectors offer numerous advantages over III-V compound semiconductors-based UV PDs, such as low cost, compassionate response, easy operation, and compactness. These photodetectors are not easily oxidized and can be easily manufactured with nanoscale electronic components, making them a subject of significant research attention [45,47,48]. MOx-based UV photodetectors with various device structures can generally be divided into four types, namely photoconductors, Schottky photodiode, junction photodiode (phototransistors), and MSM (metal-semiconductor-metal) [49] having different performance aspects and several In-field Applications, (Fig. 2a).

MOx-based UV PDs have made remarkable advancements in recent years. As shown in Fig. 2b (i), the growing number of publications on UV PDs since 1990 indicates the increasing research interest in this field. These UV PDs come in a broad range of shapes and sizes, from zero-dimensional (0D) to 3D nanostructures (NSs), making them an excellent choice for photodetection applications. Research suggests that constraining MOx NSs to 0D MOx NSs has some demerits affecting the overall performance of UV PDs including limited light absorption, reduced carrier transport efficiency, and synthesis challenges. Whereas the 1D MOx NSs, particularly nanorods (NRs), nanotubes (NTs), or nanowires (NWs) [50–53], are preferred over 0D MOx NSs due to their enhanced carrier transport, ease of functionalization, and versatility in UV PDs applications. However, the alignment challenges in 1D MOx NSs impact the overall UV PDs functionality. Constraining the MOx NSs to 2D MOx NSs i.e. thin films or nanoarrays could significantly enhance the photoresponse of UV PDs but low light absorption due to thin atomic structure and complex fabrication restrict them from being efficient MOx NSs for UV PDs. The unique self-encapsulating geometry of 3D MOx NSs specifically MOx NBs can enhance the optical and electrical stability of the UV PDs making them stable and reliable. The MOx NBs provide mechanical flexibility and strength to the MOx NSs, enabling their integration into flexible UV PDs. MOx NBs-based UV PDs demonstrate superior performance attributes while fabricating cost-effectively. The response time of UV PDs based on MOx NBs is also highly recommended, with an average response time ranging from microseconds (μ s) to milliseconds (ms) [54].

Moreover, the branching of NWs into a brush-like morphology exhibits the highest response speed due to its high surface-to-volume ratio and ease of electron flow. Fig. 2b (ii) shows the majority of research work (MOx-based materials) for the development of PDs where ZnO becomes the material of choice for developing MOx-based PDs due to its wide bandgap, high excitonic binding energy, chemical and optical stability, excellent biocompatibility, and piezoelectricity. This has significant implications for designing UV PDs where high responsivity is critical for scientific instruments or medical devices. The development of multifunctional MOx NBs-based UV PDs presents a significant breakthrough in UV PD technology. The unique NB morphology of MOx demonstrates higher response speed, responsivity, and photocurrent, making it an ideal material for UV PDs. Advanced devices have been proposed, taking into account critical elements such as responsivity, detectivity, operating voltage, photocurrent, external quantum efficiency, photoconductive gain, response time, and stability, all of which are essential for enhancing the device's absorption phenomenon and photoelectric performance. The advanced sensing performance is achieved by using NBs with a determined NWs length about the tetrapod arm diameter or by using a network of NBs instead of a single one, increasing the available surface area. The plasma parameters during etching could be altered to reduce the diameters of formed MOx NWs. To improve the sensitivity and selectivity of MOx-based UV PDs, render the hierarchical and functional ZnO NBs, which are widely engaged in various photodetection applications due to their excellent response, good detectivity, simple fabrication, tunable morphology, good thermal, optical, and chemical stability [40].

Essentially, the fundamental photodetection functionalization is influenced by converting the given optical signal (UV–visible illumination) to the electrical signal due to the emission of electrons or changing the conductivity at MOx surfaces. These MOx NBs-based UV PDs are rooted in the photoelectric phenomenon and oxygen adsorption model, which involves 3 essential steps: (i) generation of e^-h^+ pairs; (ii) transportation or multiplication of the charge carriers; (iii) extraction of the charge carriers in the form of electrical signals. The MOx NBs UV PDs are mainly defined as the branched hierarchical nanoheterostructure showing a brush-like structure that provides high-performance parameters, including sensitivity, good detectability, quick response, recovery, and high responsivity. The broad comprehensive bandgap semiconductor materials, particularly MOx (ZnO, TiO₂, CuO, NiO, and SnO₂) are widely used for UV PDs. These MOx NBs exhibit a high surface-to-volume ratio and the potential to be utilized in optoelectronic devices because of their minimal dimensional nanostructures (quantum impact). The most significant benefit of ZnO is the development of various morphologies that are helpful in PD applications. The well-accepted growth strategy for developing NBs is defined as the two-step growth process. It is considered reliable, easy to scale up, environmentally benign, and efficient in synthesising large-area nanoheterostructure [55]. The two-step growth method includes distinct growth techniques in each step for the growth of NBs, such as hydrothermal method, VLS method, pulsed laser deposition (PLD), aqueous solution method, vapor transport method, chemical reduction method, anodizing, and spin coating seed method. These distinct growth methods allow the rational design and synthesis of regulated nanostructured materials, facilitating the gradual modification and optimization within experimental conditions.

The future of these UV PDs looks incredibly promising, and their specific application fields will undoubtedly influence their development. With simultaneous advancements in multiple areas, the future of these PDs seems bright. The high surface-to-volume ratio of hierarchical NBs has piqued the interest of researchers in recent times because of their enhanced performance in nano-devices like sensors and detectors. This comprehensive review critically examines the potential of using the unique morphology of NBs for photodetection mechanisms with a fast response, highlighting the diverse photoresponse parameters and multifunctional applications of PDs. Moreover, we discuss the challenges and future perspectives of UV PDs, which overcome the material limitations, improving device performance, and exploring new applications. We emphasize the need for more flexible, transparent, portable, wearable, and real-time UV PDs to expand their in-field applications. For instance, MOx NBs-based UV PDs offer exciting opportunities for creating conformable sensors that can be integrated into wearable devices for real-time monitoring of UV exposure. Moreover, the transparency of these UV PDs makes them ideal for integration into glass surfaces for real-time monitoring of UV exposure in indoor environments. This study provides innovative ideas that MOx-based core-shell heterostructured UV PDs would address challenges and unlock new opportunities for real-world applications.

2. Growth and Synthesis Techniques for MOx NBs

MOx NBs are grown on substrates (flexible/non-flexible) or self-assembly NSs that exhibit the desirable prerequisite properties, such as simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and tuneable morphology making them suitable for direct utilization for various applications [56]. The complex heterostructured core-shell MOx NBs includes the growth of 1D NSs (e.g. TiO₂ NWs) encapsulating by another 1D NSs (e.g. ZnO NRs). These 1D NSs can be significantly developed by using different growth and synthesis techniques, such as hydrothermal, pulsed laser deposition (PLD), aqueous solution method, vapor transport method, anodizing, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), metal-organic CVD (MOCVD), atomic layer deposition (ALD), thermal evaporation, laser ablation, hetero-epitaxial growth process, electrospinning, and etching [57–59]. Hence,

typically MOx NBs can be grown on the seeded layer or self-assembly using two-step methods that combine any of two convenient growth techniques by controlling the growth parameters such as molarity, growth temperature, pH of the solution, and environment [60,61]. This section provides a comprehensive merit/demerit of various growth techniques that are currently being used for the growth of MOx NBs.

2.1. Hydrothermal method

The hydrothermal method is a remarkable and useful technique to synthesize a wide range of nanostructured materials. This method involves the use of high-temperature aqueous solutions under high vapor pressures to precisely modulate the microstructure and crystallite size of selected materials [62]. The process starts by placing reactants in an autoclave and deionized (DI) water or other solvents. The hydrothermal method facilitates the formation of desired morphologies concerning the temperature and pressure of the autoclave. This method is well-known for producing high-quality, monodispersed NSs with precise morphology, composition, and crystallinity [63].

Recently, this method has been considered for facile growth of complex hierarchical or heterostructured core-shell MOx NB's. Zou et al. prepared ZnO/TiO₂ NBs using a two-step process with the facile hydrothermal method (for NBs) and magnetron sputtering technique (for the seed layer) [64,65]. Abbas et al. synthesized the NiCo₂O₄@Carbon Cloth (NCO@CC) via a facile and scalable hydrothermal and discussed the growth mechanism (Fig. 3b) [66]. Zhang et al. successfully synthesized a branched ZnO-CdS double-shell NW arrays on the surface of a carbon fiber (CF/ZnO-CdS) using a simple two-step hydrothermal method [67]. Li et al. have grown ZnO NRs@ES-ZnO NFs via the hydrothermal method when precisely controlling the solution concentration (Fig. 3g) [68]. Sun et al. reported the controlled synthesis of 3D-ZnO nano-forests morphology via a facile hydrothermal method (Fig. 3e) [69].

Even though the hydrothermal method is a relatively simple and 'green' process, making it environmentally friendly with a synthesis of a wide range of nanomaterials including metal oxides and doped oxides [74]. Additionally, the hydrothermal method allows for control over particle morphology, that plays a crucial role in detection applications [75]. On the other hand, there are also some disadvantages to this method including poor mixing in the hydrothermal reactor causing blockages, leading to poor process reliability and product reproducibility [76]. Another challenge is the scalability of the reactor for high volume throughput, as different reactor geometries need to be compared to avoid particle accumulation during scale-up.

2.2. Aqueous solution methods

The aqueous solution method is widely used for growing NBs and other NSs. In this method, the precursors were dissolved in DI water at room temperature and then aged for different durations at required ambient conditions to manipulate the types of NSs or NBs. This method is particularly used for the growth of MOx NBs. Park et al. [70] demonstrated the process for the growth of ZnO NBs using a two-step aqueous solution (Fig. 3a). To initiate the growth of NBs, the prepared solution and a seed solution were prepared and combined, subjecting the mixture to specific conditions such as temperature, pH, and time. Fig. 3 (f), describes the precise controlling of NBs and morphology due to varying KOH concentration and reaction time [73]. Several factors, such as the concentration of precursor material, the presence of additives, and the solution processing conditions, including heating and cooling, can influence the NB's growth. The aqueous solution method offers several advantages including the ability to synthesize NBs at relatively low temperatures, scalability, and the potential to control specific properties such as morphology and composition of the NBs.

2.3. Plasma etching

Plasma etching is one of the precise and controlled processes that selectively removes material from a substrate's surface creating a plasma environment within a vacuum chamber, where a combination of ions, electrons, and reactive radicals interact with the substrate [77–79]. This technique enables the growth of intricate NBs with superior control, precision, selectivity, and speed. This level of precision allows for the selective removal of material while preserving another substrate area. It is a high-speed etching process and efficiently works with different substrates and materials [80]. The chemically balanced surfaces created on NBs produced by plasma etching for various applications. In summary, plasma etching plays a crucial role in the growth of NBs, especially MOx NBs, by providing precise control, high selectivity, and the ability to create unique NSs with desirable properties for different applications [81]. Nevertheless, the implementation of plasma etching in a fabrication process of NSs and devices requires careful consideration to avoid limitations. This method requires a high voltage, substrate compatibility issues, complexity of process control, and potential for surface damage, uniformity challenges, and environmental concerns [82]. Addressing these limitations are crucial to ensure the successful and reliable implementation of plasma etching. Kohlmann et al. employed a plasma etching technique for the fabrication of ZnO NBs. They selectively etched the material in a hydrogen-acetylene (H₂-C₂H₂) plasma, which proved to be most effective with a 1 % C₂H₂ admixture [71]. The presence of C₂H₂ enabled the formation of NWs arrays through sidewall passivation due to a-C:H deposition. This technique has been highly beneficial in producing ZnO NBs with a high surface-to-volume ratio (Fig. 3c).

2.4. Other methods

The other growth techniques can also be employed for the growth of NBs, including Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) [83], Spray Pyrolysis [84], NB-Shearing Technology (NBST) and seed hetero-epitaxial growth method (Fig. 3d) [72]. These techniques offer some unique advantages and capabilities of NB morphology fabrication for various applications. The PLD facilitates the growth of MOx NB architectures through the precise control of growth conditions [85]. The critical aspect of forming these NBs is to strike a balance between defect aggregation and surface-smoothing processes by regulating atomic surface transport processes. According to high-resolution microscopy data, the aggregation of defects plays a pivotal role in MOx NB's growth. The high concentration of defects at the intersection of domain boundaries promotes the aggregation of PLD growth species, which results in the formation of the single-crystalline NB architecture [86]. However, optimizing PLD parameters is essential to achieve the desired morphology and properties. A better understanding of the interplay between defect creation and growth mode is necessary to apply this method to a broader range of NSs. Fan et al. prepared a single-crystalline anatase TiO₂ NBs architecture with large surface area demonstrating the precise control of non-equilibrium growth conditions [87].

Spray pyrolysis is a CVD technique that entails spraying a solution of the desired material onto a heated substrate. Once the solution is sprayed, it decomposes and reacts to form the desired NSs [88]. This process employs ultrasonic nebulizers to generate a fine aerosol of the precursor solution. By adjusting parameters (precursor concentration, temperature, and residence time), this method allows for precise control over the size and morphology of NBs [89]. It is a scalable and continuous process, making it a suitable choice for the industrial production of NBs. Overall, spray pyrolysis is a highly effective method for the growth of metallic and other types of NBs, owing to its ability to produce high-quality nanostructures in a simple and controllable manner.

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the growth of (a) ZnO NBs using two-step aqueous solution method [70]; (b) $NiCo_2O_4@CC$ NBs via hydrothermal method [66]; (c) 3D ZnO NBs array via hydrothermal method Reproduced with permission @ACS [71]; (d) Cu@ZnO NBs via the seed hetero-epitaxial growth approach [72]; (e) ZnO NBs grown on ZnO NWs array using hydrothermal method [69]; (f) ZnO 3D hierarchical NSs using two-step aqueous solution method and schematically representing the morphology variation under varying KOH concentration and reaction timing Reproduced with permission @RSC [73]; (g) ZnO NRs @ ZnO NFs using electrospinning and hydrothermal method Reproduced with permission @Elsevier [68].

3. Photodetection mechanism of NBs-based UV PDs

MOx NBs are introduced as the best candidate for the photodetection application that improves stability, detectivity, efficiency, and fast response time due to their high surface-to-volume ratio and low potential at the junction interface [90,91]. The fundamental detecting mechanism underlying MOx NBs-based UV-PDs is rooted in their morphological advancement, when 1D MOx NSs are encapsulated over another 1D NSs, there is an enhancement in surface-to-volume ratio resulting in significant absorption of photons or oxygen molecules in ambient air on the surface of MOx-NBs [92]. This leads to a narrower depletion region and easy movement of excited carriers allowing a gradual increase in current, leading to higher responsivity [93,94]. The UV response mechanism of MOx NBs is explained with the schematic structure in Fig. 4.

The encapsulated 1D MOx NSs surface states (Fig. 4a) attract intermediates oxygen (O₂), capturing free electrons leading to the bonded negatively charged ions (O⁻²) i.e. the formation of band bending or a

low junction potential at the MOx-atmosphere interface.

The junction potential is the influential factor for the functioning of MOx-based devices. A lower junction potential creates a narrower depletion region allowing faster movement of charge carriers, reducing their recombination rate [95]. Moreover, the higher junction potential affects the overall performance of the UV PDs and their ability to detect weak or low-light signals. To mitigate low light detection in MOx-based UV PDs, NBs have shown the potential due to high surface-to-volume ratio to enhance the sensitivity and performance of PDs at low illumination [96,97]. Therefore, the narrower depletion region and weak signal detection associated with a low junction potential are key factors in optimizing the photodetection performances of NSs seeking high responsivity and fast response time. Under UV light illumination [98], higher e⁻ & h⁺ pairs are generated due to higher surface-to-volume ratio and photogenerated h⁺ interact with oxygen ions (O⁻²) to form

Fig. 4. (a) Schematic illustration of the primary mechanism of MOx NBs-based UV PDs and inset the magnified nanobrushes; (b) Energy band diagram of simple core-shell MOx NSs; (c) Energy band diagram of heterostructured core-shell MOx NBs.

intermediates oxygen (O₂). Now, more charge carriers (e⁻) would easily transport from a narrower depletion region to the interface of MO_x NSs, enhancing photo-induced potential, conductivity, and photocurrent.

The photodetection mechanism of simple core-shell MO_x NSs and core-shell MO_x NBs through the energy band diagram is explained schematically (Fig. 4 b & c). Fig. 4 (b) shows the simple core-shell MO_x NSs along with a wider depletion layer and lower carrier generation under UV illumination associated with comparably higher junction potential ($\phi_{cs} > \phi_{NB}$), lower surface-to-volume ratio, and lower interaction with O₂. However, the core-shell MO_x NBs have a narrower depletion layer and higher charge carrier generation under UV illumination associated with comparably lower junction potential ($\phi_{cs} < \phi_{NB}$), higher surface-to-volume ratio, and higher interaction with O₂ [99] (Fig. 4 c). Consequently, the core-shell MO_x NBs have easier and faster photo-generated charge carriers transport in UV PDs initiating an understanding to manipulate the photodetection mechanism by embedding MO_x NSs morphology [100]. In principle, the variation in electrical and optical properties serves as a reliable indicator for the MO_x NBs-based UV PDs and results in several prospective advantages, including (i) elevated fast response speed due to decreased depletion layer or the junction potential; (ii) enhanced responsivity and detectivity to active UV illumination; (iii) significant external quantum efficiency (EQE) due to high surface-to-volume ratio and periodic arrangement of NBs; and (iv) clearer insight through variation in the electrical and optical properties for better functioning self-powered UV PDs. This knowledge holds a promise for developing more efficient and accurate UV PDs that find application in optoelectronic fields, including imagining celestial bodies, energy generation (solar cells)[101,102], optical

communications, security, bio-imaging, and video imaging[103–105].

According to the literature survey, MO_x NBs-based UV PDs reveal photo-detecting mechanisms with improved performance owing to excellent chemical/thermal stability, non-toxicity, and lower fabrication cost [106]. Even though various MO_x NBs-based UV PDs have been used for UV PDs, including SnO₂, Co₃O₄, CuO, TiO₂, ZnO, WO₃, and Fe₂O₃ along with tuning the microstructure (Fig. 5), these MO_x faces challenges in terms of efficiency and stability. The lower bandgap of these MO_x facilitates the absorption of visible spectra enabling less efficiency in carrier transport along with planar structure [27]. In the case of MO_x NPs with a higher surface area, there is trapping of electrons which restricts their function as effective PDs [107]. However among MO_x, ZnO, SnO₂, and TiO₂ are preferred, and discussed in detail the merits/demerits due to favorable operating conditions ($\lambda = 100\text{--}400\text{ nm}$) [108], wide bandgap (3.37, 3.6, and 3.2 eV) [109,110] and high excitonic binding energy (60, 130, and 90 meV) [111], respectively. These MO_x-based NB PDs are extensively engaged in various photodetection applications (Fig. 1) because they absorb more UV light and produce an excess of photocurrent [112–115].

3.1. ZnO NBs-based UV PDs

ZnO has been recognized as an economically feasible and low-toxic material, garnering substantial research and application in the past few decades[43,116,117]. ZnO's vital properties, including a wide bandgap, chemical and optical stability, excellent biocompatibility, and piezoelectricity, enable it to be optimal for an extensive range of applications. Consequently, ZnO has been employed in numerous functional components of optoelectronics, microelectronics [49], energy generation (e.g., solar cells), microfluidics devices, and many more

Fig. 5. Schematic classification of various MO_x NBs-based UV PDs.

applications [54,108,109,118]. The morphology and surface structure adjustment is commonly needed to further tailor its properties to these applications. Distinct morphologies of ZnO, including nanorods (NRs) [59], nanowires (NWs) [119], nanosheets [120], nanoflowers [121],

nanodumbbell [122], nanotetrapods [123], nanosponges [124], nanosphere, and other offering unique advantages with a high surface-to-volume ratio and high compatibility for UV PDs that can be synthesized. Recently, core-shell nanoheterostructures of ZnO crystals

Fig. 6. (a) Schematic diagram showing the carrier generation, transportation process and detection mechanism in the ZnO NB-based UV PDs, Reproduced with permission@Wiley[128]. (b) Ag NW@S-ZnO NR-based UV detector; (c-d) Ag NW@S-ZnO NR-based UV PDs with different bending angles, switching performance and corresponding response time; (e) Electron flow path in Ag NW@ZnO NRs; (f) Energy band diagram of ZnO NRs/Ag NWs in dark and under UV light, Reproduced with the permission @Elsevier[129]. (g) Schematic illustration of carrier transportation in single Ag NW-ZnO heteronanowire, Reproduced with permission @ACS[130].

have become the focus of research, where individual core-shell nano heterostructures and an array are being investigated [124–126]. Among all these core-shell nano heterostructures, the hierarchical ZnO NBs are highly suitable for UV PDs due to their high compatibility, efficiency, and convenience [30,127].

For ZnO NBs-based UV PDs, Alenezi et al. developed the hierarchical ZnO NBs built from initial mono-morphological nanomaterials, ZnO NWs, and ZnO nanoplates (ZNP) using sequential nucleation and growth following a hydrothermal process [128]. The hierarchical NMs showed improved UV detection, as well as enhanced sensitivity ($\sim 10^4$), an ultra-fast response time (~ 235 ms), and a good recovery time (~ 310 ms). Moreover, the enhanced sensitivity of ZnO NBs PDs occurred because of the reduced dimensionality and the ultrahigh surface-to-volume ratio. Fig. 6(a) shows the generation, transportation, and detection mechanism in ZnO NBs-based UV PDs where oxygen vacancies (V_O) in ZnO donate electrons to its conduction band and produce a low-conductivity depletion layer closer to the surface. Here, the negative charges at the surface create band bending extending into the quantum confinement vertical to the surface, producing a surface potential barrier. Consequently, the conductivity of ZnO NBs-based PD is controlled by a mechanism as its structure contains nanojunctions with the initial and secondary ZnO NWs. The initial and secondary depletion regions of ZnO NWs act as barriers to electron movement and are also the predominant modulators of charge transport. Therefore, controlling the charge transport concerning two consecutive nanojunctions, Schottky barriers, improves the response and recovery times of ZnO NB-based PDs [128].

Zhang et al. fabricated Ag NW@S-ZnO NRs PDs using a two-step method in an oil bath and drop-coating with different drop-coating times on the polyethylene terephthalate (PET) surface coupled with Au electrodes. Under UV light illumination (365 nm with a bias of 5 V), PDs exhibit an extensive sensitivity of over $\sim 10^3$, a lower response/recovery time of 2.6/2.3 sec, and an average transmittance of more than 70 % in the visible light region [129]. Fig. 6(b) shows the final structure of the fabricated Ag NW@S-ZnO NRs UV PDs. A pair of Au electrodes with a distance of 26 mm were realized by magnetron sputtering. Fig. 6(c) shows the images of PDs with different bending angles. The switching performance and response time of PDs at different bending angles showed the unaffected photocurrent and had a negligible effect on the response time (in the range of 2–3 sec), as shown in Fig. 6(d). The working mechanism of Ag NW@S-ZnO NRs-based UV PDs with high sensitivity and response speed are shown in Fig. 6(e–f).

The electron transport path of Ag NWs@ZnO NR-based UV PD is shown in Fig. 6(e). Where Fig. 6(f) shows the energy bandgap of ZnO/Ag NWs, elaborating the formation of a high resistive depletion layer near the ZnO NRs surface caused by two factors: (i) the difference in the work function of Ag NWs (~ 4.69 eV) and ZnO (~ 4.35 eV) resulting in the flow of electrons in ZnO into Ag NWs until the Fermi level is aligned [97, 131]. (ii) The absorption of oxygen molecules on the ZnO NRs surface capturing of free electrons at the conduction band [132]. The formation of the high resistive depletion layer and the built-in-field between ZnO NRs and Ag NWs improves the separation and transport of photo-generated electron-hole pairs, resulting in a high response speed. Furthermore, these flexible and transparent Ag NW@ZnO NRs-based UV PDs show significant potential in practical applications and mass production with simple and inexpensive fabrication processes and excellent integral performances.

Yang et al. synthesized Ag NWs-ZnO branched NRs (BNRs) hetero-nanowires using an enhanced two-step hydrothermal method. The fabricated hetero-NWs are aligned on the Au electrode with the dielectrophoresis method, improving flexibility and operability, a maximum photocurrent of 0.25 mA, large responsivity of 2.5 AW^{-1} , and a shortened response time of 1 s [130]. Fig. 6(g) analyzes the photoresponse mechanism of Ag NW-ZnO BNRs hetero-nanowire-based UV PDs on the adsorption and desorption of oxygen molecules on the surface. Firstly, the ZnO BNRs are exposed to photon energy (>3.32 eV) to generate the

electron-hole pairs. Secondly, the photo-generated holes recombine with the O^{2-} and trap the electron while migrating to the ZnO to release O_2 from the surface. Moreover, the excellent photoresponse performance is attributed to the structure superiority of hetero-NWs, including improvement in light harvesting and oxygen molecule adsorption/desorption efficiencies, the more effective interface between electron-hole pairs, and the higher mobility benefiting from collecting and transporting more number of carriers.

Rong et al. successfully have grown ZnO NRs and 3D SnO_2 octahedron nano-blocks (ONBs) on ITO substrates using hydrothermal and RF magnetron sputtering (Fig. 7a). The fabricated UV PDs exhibited remarkable stability and repeatability under the exposure of UV light. The photoresponsivity was also observed relatively high due to high photocurrent density (0.94 mAcm^{-2}) along with an enhanced on/off ratio of amount 5362 [133]. Zhang et al. synthesized a branched ZnO-CdS double-shell (DS) NW array on a carbon fiber (CF) surface using a facile two-step hydrothermal method. Under UV light, the device exhibits photoresponsivity of $1.94 \times 10^5 \text{ A/W}$ and intensity of $1.59 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W/cm}$ [67]. Fig. 7(b) shows the growth of the branched ZnO-CdS DSNW array, where the CF was first coated on ITO substrate and ZnO seed layer was coated further for better adherence and high conductivity. Finally, the hydrothermal method was used to grow CdS NW arrays on ZnO NWs. Fig. 7(c) shows the schematic structure of the fabricated PD device. The fabricated PDs with a typical length of ~ 1 cm, the width of ~ 1 cm, and thickness of 0.5 mm were fixed on a PS substrate tightly by using the silver paste (Fig. 7d). The corresponding energy band diagram for mechanism is given in Fig. 7(e). Therefore, the potential for broadband photodetection with ultrahigh photoresponsivity has been concluded.

Zhang et al. synthesized 3D-branched hierarchical 3 C-SiC/ZnO heterostructures using a three-step process, including hydrothermal and carbonization, to apply UV PDs practically. The outstanding photo-detection performance was achieved with an ultrahigh EQE ($1.69 \times 10^8\%$), significant responsivity ($4.8 \times 10^5 \text{ A/W}$), rapid response time (rise time of 40 ms and decay time of 60 ms) [134]. Fig. 7(f) shows the schematic design of the prepared PD devices. The schematic illustration of the energy band diagrams of 1D ZnO nanowire and hierarchical 3D-branched 3 C-SiC/ZnO heterostructure. The 1D ZnO nanowire and 3D 3 C-SiC/ZnO heterostructures PDs with superior optoelectronic conversion efficiency are given in Fig. 7(g–h). Furthermore, it gives an excellent photo-detection performance with a high photo/dark current ratio of 187.8. It demonstrates photocurrent stability and reproducibility, which are advantageous or comparable to ZnO and other inorganic semiconductor-based PDs. Zhang et al. synthesized highly-crystalline CdS/ZnO branched nanoheterostructures using a two-step process: thermal vapor deposition and hydrothermal method. The photodetection performance of an individual CdS/ZnO branched heterostructure PD was achieved with an On/Off ratio (81) and a rise time of ~ 250 ms. The CdS/ZnO branched heterostructures were found to have a significant performance for optoelectronic applications concerning the photocurrent to dark current ratio and responsivity [136]. The low response time concludes that NBs' heterostructure absorbs more light energy and effectively produces carriers for transport rather than promoting their recombination and the best morphology for the practical application of PDs [137].

Shao et al. fabricated a flexible, thorn-like ZnO-multiwalled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) hybrid paper for efficient UV sensing and photocatalyst applications via atomic layer deposition (ALD) and hydrothermal growth [135]. Fig. 7 (i) schematically shows the fabricated ZnO/MWCNT UV PD device deposited on the hybrid paper. The carrier generation and transport mechanism of ZnO/MWCNT hybrid paper is given in Fig. 7 (j). When oxygen molecules bind to the oxide's surface and capture free electrons, this culminates in the growth of a low-conductivity depletion layer closer to the ZnO surface. Due to its high surface-to-volume ratio, the ZnO-MWCNT hybrid paper exhibits a high density of hole-trap states on the surface. As seen in the mechanism (Fig. 7 j) under UV illumination, the electron-hole pairs are created and

Fig. 7. (a) Schematic representation of self-powered Z/S hierarchical heterostructured-based UV PDs; (b) Single CF/ZnO-CdS NBs; (c) the design for the single CF/ZnO-CdS NBs-based device; (d) Design of single CF/ZnO-CdS NW-based PDs; (e) Energy band diagram of a strain-free single CF/ZnO-CdS NWs-based device, Reproduced with permission @ACS [67]; (f) The design for 3D-branched hierarchical 3 C-SiC/ZnO heterostructures PDs device; (g-h) The band diagram describing the photodetection mechanism of 1D ZnO NWs and 3D branched 3 C-SiC/ZnO PD respectively, Reproduced with permission @RSC [134]; (i) The UV PDs fabricated from ZnO-MWCNT hybrid paper; (j) Transportation, detection, and photoconduction mechanism of the ZnO-MWCNT hybrid PDs under dark and UV illumination, Reproduced with permission @RSC [135].

transferred, leaving the trapped holes on the branched surface. Through an external bias voltage, the unpaired electrons rapidly move to the MWCNT and flow in the direction of the electrode. The trapped holes recombine with the negatively charged oxygen ions, allowing neutral oxygen molecules to be desorbed from the surface of ZnO branches. Table 1 presents a brief comparison of photodetection parameters for different ZnO NSs, including 0D, 1D, 2D, and 3D NSs, with the NBs-based UV PDs. Different ZnO NSs, including 0D, 1D, 2D, and 3D NSs, are highlighted with their performance indices for UV PDs. It can be concluded that although some ZnO NSs exhibit good results in certain circumstances, the most effective performance in UV PDs is achieved through the hierarchical or heterostructured ZnO NBs.

Tang et al. fabricated CdS-MoS₂ coated ZnO NBs and prepared the photoelectrode on FTO using the chemical bath deposition (CBD). The self-powered ternary brush-like photoelectrode exhibited better photoelectrochemical (PEC) performance with a photocurrent density of 20.32 mA/cm² attributed to the high light absorption with significant band alignment and stable lifetime [166]. Consequently, the performance of core-shell ZnO/CdS/MoS₂ NBs has prodigious potential in photodetection, photocatalysis, and other optoelectronic applications.

3.2. SnO₂ NBs-based UV PDs

Tin oxide (SnO₂) has a rutile phase tetragonal structure, wide bandgap (3.62 eV), high exciton binding energy (~130 meV), and higher electron mobility (100–200 cm²V⁻¹S⁻¹) [167]. It is comparatively more thermodynamically stable and is an ideal material showing unique optical and electronic properties for optoelectronics, gas sensors, energy storage/conversion, and specifically for UV PDs [168–170]. Nanostructured SnO₂-based UV PD performance includes high sensitivity, significant photocurrent gain, good reliability, and fast response time, which is achieved by manipulating their morphology, dimensions, crystallite orientation, surface features, and grains network [171]. Table 2 summarised the comparative study of various SnO₂ based UV PDs in terms of responsivity, detectivity & response time along with their preparation techniques. Lin et al. reported SnO₂ NWs and discovered the optical gain, which can reach as high as 10⁴ in air and 10⁵ in vacuum. The detecting mechanism not only emphasizes the neutralization of ionized oxygen molecules by trapping holes, $h^+ + O_2^- \rightarrow O_2$ but also points out the significant role of the space charges induced by defects, extending the carrier lifetime significantly [172]. However, the SnO₂-based UV PDs (NWs, NRs, Nanotubes, and so on) with all ideal parameters and corresponding nanoarrays have employed expensive techniques but still trail behind in cost, practical application, rapid response, and considerable photocurrent production. The SnO₂ NBs heterostructure in these circumstances stands out with the higher surface-to-volume ratio, significant photocurrent, and simplicity. Lower-cost synthesis methods are preferred for the development of practical UV PDs. It is concluded that the paper-based functional SnO₂ NBs with metal and MO_x have shown better UV PDs.

Marimuthu et al. prepared an efficacious SnO₂ NBs using a hot wall nebulizer spray pyrolysis technique for different precursor concentrations, showing significant performance at low light intensity (0.2 mW/cm²) at low bias voltage (0.4 mV) with rise/decay times are 250/506 ms, photocurrent 1.43 nA, and the responsivity 15 mA/W [188]. Fig. 8 (a) shows the device structure of the fabricated SnO₂ NBs UV PDs at 5 V bias. Fig. 8(b-d) systematically explained the transient photoresponse properties of SnO₂, revealing the improved decay time constants and stable photocurrent. Under low illumination, the oxygen molecules present in the atmosphere are chemically absorbed and then ionized by capturing free electrons on NBs surface, resulting in a less-conducting depletion layer (O₂⁻) (Fig. 8 b). Upon UV light exposure, the generation of electron-hole pairs and recombination of photo-generated holes with the oxygen-trapped electrons occur on the NB surface. These roots allow the desorption of oxygen from the surface and

result in the reduction of the depletion layer (Fig. 8 c). Fig. 8 (d) shows the further transient photoresponse of SnO₂-based PDs when it is turned off. The log scale plot of I-V curves is given in Fig. 8 (e), which indicates the photo-to-dark current ratio at 0.02 M concentration. Moreover, the enhanced device parameters concluded that the photosensitivity has a linear relationship with dark/photocurrent and is inversely proportional to the depletion layer width (Fig. 8 f).

Dai et al. synthesised SnO₂ NWs by vapor transport method, and hierarchical ZnO NRs were grown hydrothermally around the SnO₂ NWs to form SnO₂/ZnO NBs heterostructure with a high surface-to-volume ratio. Under UV illumination (325 nm), the developed PD showed improved reversibility and response speed with a photocurrent of 40 μA and a response time of 622 ms [165]. Fig. 8 (g) shows the fabricated SnO₂/ZnO hierarchical structure's final device structure based on UV PDs. The PL spectrum comprises three subbands at 390 nm, 425 nm, and 520 nm, as shown in Fig. 8 (h) [190]. The SnO₂/ZnO NBs proposed distinct and more enhanced PL spectra than the SnO₂ NWs for the following reasons: (i) the defect on SnO₂ NWs surface may be compensated by the ZnO NRs [191], (ii) the ZnO NRs surround the SnO₂ NWs, then the excitation light was almost absorbed by the ZnO NRs, not by the SnO₂ NWs; and (iii) the PL peak from the SnO₂ can't be detected, indicating the weaker PL from the SnO₂ NWs than that from ZnO NRs. Fig. 8 (i) shows the photocurrent response and fall-off processes under on/off UV light exposure at 5 V bias with multiple cycles of 100 sec, where the dark current is 3.0×10⁻⁶ A and photocurrent is 4.0×10⁻⁵ A. Subsequently, the synthesized hierarchical NSs with controlled morphology and the hierarchical SnO₂/ZnO NBs based UV PDs results explicitly in faster time constant with high responsivity, detectivity and photocurrent.

Chen et al. fabricated the self-powered SnO₂-TiO₂ NBs array-based UV PDs using a simple fabrication process, i.e. a soft chemical technique (Fig. 8 j). Under UV light (365 nm) irradiation, the PD device exhibits a significantly high responsivity of 0.145 A/W with a fast rise and decay time of 37 and 15 ms and highly stable spectral selectivity [189]. Fig. 8 (k) presents a schematic illustration of the energy band mechanism of UV PDs having enhanced device performance. The photocurrent response had achieved the periodic on/off cycle at every 10 sec (Fig. 8 l). Huang et al. synthesized ZnS/SnO₂ core-shell (CS) heterostructured ribbons for the first time by using a simple two-step thermal evaporation approach. An electrical property of the synthesized ZnS/SnO₂ CS heterostructure was investigated by constructing a FET, exhibiting a high on/off ratio of ~10³ and an increased mobility of ~33.2 cm² V⁻¹s⁻¹. Moreover, the optoelectronic properties of the sample are also investigated, which showed good operating performances, including large photocurrent, high sensitivity (high R and EQE values), good stability and reproducibility, and relatively fast response speed [192].

3.3. TiO₂ NBs-based UV PDs

TiO₂ has been extensively studied and emphasized owing to its unique electrochemical, optoelectronic, and electrophysical properties, which make them promising for n-type semiconductor devices [193] in many fields, including UV sensors, dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) [194,195] and UV PDs [196,197]. TiO₂ NSs feature wide bandgap (anatase 3.2 eV and rutile 3.0 eV), high stability, non-toxicity, abundant availability, cost-efficiency, significant electron mobility, and lower defect concentration [198–200]. In particular, 1-D TiO₂ NSs, including NRs, NWs, nanopencils, and nanotubes, are more desirable, considering their enormous specific surface area and a well-defined charge carrier transport path (Table 3).

Gao et al. synthesized NiO/TiO₂ NRs and NiO/TiO₂ NRs/TiO_x for the high-performance self-powered UV PDs application with rise/decay times of 38.5/4.2 sec and 28.9/2.0 sec, the photocurrent of 0.3 and 0.4 μA, and the responsivity of 1.34 and 5.66 mA/W, respectively [211]. Xue et al. fabricated nanocrystalline TiO₂ thin film-based UV PDs using

Table 1
Parameter comparison for different ZnO NSs based UV PDs.

ZnO NSs	Wavelength (nm)	Preparation techniques	Voltage (V)	Response time (s)	Responsivity (mA/W)	I _{photo} (μA)	Detectivity (jones)	Ref.
0D NSs								
ZnO NPs coated Au/ZnO/Au	376	Magnetron sputtering	3	0.24	52	51 × 10 ⁻³	-	[138]
ZnO NPs film	-	Swelling controlled cracking method	2	15	2.2×10 ⁷	0.201	7.5 × 10 ⁹	[139]
ZnO/Si-GaN	365	MOCVD	0.5	29	960	-	4.87 × 10 ⁹	[140]
Co ²⁺ :ZnO NPs/Sn	375	Spin-coating polyol method	0.74	0.62	5500	50.57 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.3 × 10 ¹³	[141]
Te/ZnO NPs	350	Low-cost writing method	0	2.46	387	0.5 × 10 ⁻³	4.0 × 10 ¹⁰	[142]
Ag/ZnMgO/ZnO	275	Plasma assisted MBE	0	2.4	16	0.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	5 × 10 ⁹	[143]
1D NSs								
ZnO Nanowires	365	CVD	5	590	0.5	280	160	[144]
ZnO NRs	365	Aqueous solution method	0.5	100	-	1.55	-	[145]
ZnO microrod	325	Vapor phase transport	5	6.28	4 × 10 ⁴	45	-	[32]
ZnO nanotube	325	Wet-chemical reaction	0	900	0.0571	-	-	[146]
ZnO NRs/ZnO QDs	440	Solgel method	0	5	5	4	1.45 × 10 ¹⁰	[147]
ZnO/Au NWs	325	CVD	0	0.4	-	6 × 10 ⁻³	-	[148]
Sb:ZnO Nanobelts	325	CVD	0	22	0.15	0.1 × 10 ⁻³	9.9 × 10 ⁸	[149]
Single ZnO NWs	365	Hydrothermal	2	11	2400	1.2	8.2 × 10 ³	[128]
ZnO Nanodisk	365	Spin coating and Hydrothermal	3	15	3386	-	1.2 × 10 ⁴	[150]
2D Thin films								
ZnO TFs	365	chemical spray pyrolysis	5	-	31.56	65.68	-	[151]
ZnO TFs	365	Chemical bath deposition	5	9	28140	113.83	-	[152]
Ti:ZnO TFs	365	chemical spray pyrolysis	5	-	51	112.68	-	[151]
ZnO TF/Au wire	350	PLD	1	3.3	10	75	10 ¹⁰	[153]
Cu ₂ O/ZnO NWs	240	MOCVD	0	0.09	0.7 × 10 ⁻³	-	-	[41]
3D NSs & Nanoarrays								
ZnO tetrapods	325	CVD	0.2	3.5	-	1.1 × 10 ⁻³	-	[154]
Ag-modified ZnO NW arrays	365	Hydrothermal method	0	0.14	370	0.69	-	[155]
ZnO nanoneedle array	365	Hydrothermal method	0.5	0.050	22	0.8	-	[156]
Ga ₂ O ₃ -ZnO MWs	251	CVD	0	0.0001	9.7	37.5 × 10 ⁻³	6.29 × 10 ¹²	[157]
GaN/ZnO NAs	325	Hydrothermal	0	0.0069	2820	10.68 × 10 ³	6.82 × 10 ¹³	[158]
ZnO NR/GaN NT	325	Solgel method	1	1.12	3.2 × 10 ⁶	0.3 × 10 ³	7.0 × 10 ¹¹	[159]
ZnO /PANI NRs	365	Hydrothermal	0	1.35	4.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	52.8	-	[160]
ZnS/ZnO BNWs	320	Thermal evaporation and hydrothermal method	10	0.77	-	32.9 × 10 ⁻⁶	-	[161]
ZnO NR/CuO SAN arrays	365	Thermal evaporation and hydrothermal method	0	27	0.272	25 × 10 ⁻³	-	[162]
ZnO/Cu ₂ O NWs	365	Wet chemical process	5	2.3 × 10 ⁻⁵	-	135	-	[163]
Hierarchical ZnO NBs	365	two-step hydrothermal method	-	0.235	10 ⁴	-	8.2 × 10 ³	[128]
Single Ag NW@ZnO NRs	365	two-step hydrothermal method	5	1	2.5	0.25 × 10 ³	-	[130]
Ag NW@ZnO NRs	365	two-step hydrothermal method	5	2.6	6.5 × 10 ⁻⁶	10 ⁻⁶	-	[129]
ZnO-CdS branched DS NW	372	facile two-step hydrothermal method	2	-	1.94 × 10 ⁵	4.4	-	[67]
SiC/ZnO NBs	350	Hydrothermal and carbonization process	1	0.040	4.8 × 10 ⁵	18 × 10 ⁻³	1.69 × 10 ⁸	[134]
Thorn-like ZnO-MWCNT NSs	375	ALD and hydrothermal method	5	0.029	45.1	0.013 × 10 ⁶	14927	[135]
ZnO/Cu ₂ O-NB	-	Hydrothermal and chemical bath deposition techniques	-	0.14	-	19.3 × 10 ³	-	[91]
CO ₃ O ₄ -ZnO NBs film	360	two-step hydrothermal method	0	0.020	80.3	0.68 × 10 ³	-	[164]
SnO ₂ /ZnO hierarchical NBs	-	hydrothermal	5	0.622	-	40	-	[165]

Table 2
Parameter comparison for different SnO₂ NSs-based UV PDs.

SnO ₂ NSs	Wavelength (nm)	Preparation techniques	Voltage (V)	Response time (s)	Responsivity (mA/W)	I _{photo} (μA)	Detectivity (jones)	Ref.
0D NSs								
SnO ₂ NPs	300	liquid-phase exfoliation (LPE) method	0	–	0.1 × 10 ⁻³	–	–	[173]
SnO ₂ -QD/Gr	370	CVD method	0.21	0.1 × 10 ⁻³	967.6 × 10 ³	–	1.8 × 10 ¹³	[174]
SnO ₂ microspheres	325	Hydrothermal method	5	–	–	15.4	–	[175]
SnO ₂ hollow nanospheres	385	Hydrothermal method	10	100	2680 × 10 ³	10 × 10 ³	–	[176]
1D NSs								
SnO ₂ NWs	365	DC sputtering	1	50	–	19.4 × 10 ⁻³	–	[177]
Sb: SnO ₂ NWs	254	VLS method	1	1	6.25 × 10 ³	1	–	[178]
SnO ₂ NWs	–	–	0.1	100	–	200 × 10 ⁻³	–	[172]
2D NSs								
SnO ₂ TFs	320	Spin coating method	5	40 × 10 ⁻³	2.160	13 × 10 ⁻³	1.38 × 10 ¹³	[179]
SnO ₂ TFs	300	VLS method	2	4.96	2.040	27 × 10 ⁻³	–	[180]
Zn: SnO ₂ TFs	276	Spray pyrolysis deposition	1	8.78	–	1.179 × 10 ³	4.5 × 10 ⁷	[181]
SnO ₂ Nanobelts	300	CVD method	10	–	56	140 × 10 ⁻³	–	[182]
SnO ₂ NWs array	370	glancing angle deposition technique	1	0.72	0.36	0.125 × 10 ⁻³	3.02 × 10 ⁹	[183]
ZnO–SnO ₂ NWs array	300	Electrospinning method	2	0.63	–	38.1 × 10 ⁻³	–	[184]
SnO ₂ NWs arrays	254	CVD method	10	–	660 × 10 ³	1.23 × 10 ⁻³	1.12 × 10 ¹⁶	[185]
3D NSs								
Ω-shaped SnO ₂ @ZnO NSs	280	ALD	5	–	0.1 × 10 ⁶	15 × 10 ⁻³	–	[186]
ZnS/SnO ₂ core/shell ribbon	320	thermal evaporation method	1	8	–	3.2	–	[187]
SnO ₂ NB	–	spray pyrolysis	5	2.50 × 10 ⁻⁵	15	1.43 × 10 ⁻³	–	[188]
SnO ₂ @TiO ₂	365	Soft chemical process	0	0.037	145	–	–	[189]
SnO ₂ /ZnO NBS	325	Vapour transport method	0	0.622 s	–	40	–	[165]
1D-ZnO NRs/ 3D-SnO ₂ ONBs	365	liquid phase deposition and hydrothermal method	0	–	–	0.94 × 10 ³	–	[133]

the sol-gel method with Au Schottky contacts. The enhanced response parameters, including dark current (1.9 nA at 5 V), responsivity (199 A/W), and response/recovery time of 6/15 sec under UV irradiation (260 nm) [201]. Despite the promising photodetecting parameters of NSs array-based UV PDs, their performance is affected by certain drawbacks, such as low photocurrent and slow response/recovery time caused by defect traps. As a result, these factors render the prepared devices unsuitable for practical use in UV PDs. When compared to different morphological NSs of conventional wide bandgap semiconductors (ZnO, SnO₂), UV PDs using TiO₂ NBs are considered an ideal approach due to their ease of fabrication, high surface-to-volume ratio, and cost-effectiveness. Additionally, TiO₂ NBs are highly tunable and have the potential for large-scale production at a reasonable cost, making them an attractive option for UV PDs. Xie et al. fabricated TiO₂ NB arrays on the FTO glasses using a facile two-step chemical synthesis process. Fig. 9 (a) shows the schematic diagram of TiO₂ NB arrays of UV PDs. The fabrication procedure of TiO₂ NBs arrays on the FTO substrate (Fig. 9 b). Without a template, TiO₂ NB arrays had been intelligently set and assembled. Arrays of vertically aligned TiO₂ NR were grown on the FTO surface. Fig. 9 (c) depicts the potential electron transport mechanism of UV PDs of TiO₂ NB arrays. Due to I⁻/I⁻³ redox couples, the photocurrent can be renewed during UV light exposure. Nano-branches absorb UV photons with energies more remarkable than the bandgap of TiO₂, which subsequently induce electron-hole pairs in the nano-branches by promoting electrons from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB).

Through the single crystalline TiO₂ NRs, the photogenerated electrons at the interface of TiO₂/electrolyte are transported very fast to the collecting FTO substrates. These electrons reach the counter electrode, contributing to the external electricity. The separated holes lead to the counter electrode as follows: 3I⁻ + 2h⁺ → I₃⁻. The electrons accumulated at the Pt cathode will recover the electrolyte to 'I' and complete the circuit, allowing for the removal of holes from the surface of TiO₂: I₃⁻ + 2e⁻ → 3I⁻. Under a 365 nm UV LED on/off switching irradiation on TiO₂ NR arrays, the short-circuit current density (J_{SC}) and open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) of PDs were observed at only 31 μAcm⁻² and 0.32 V under 2 mWcm⁻² UV light irradiation. The response and decay time are achieved at 0.15 and 0.05 sec, indicating the rapid photoresponse and significant stability characteristics (Fig. 9 d). However, the simple device fabrication process and the outstanding UV-detecting features make these self-powered PDs a promising candidate for future applications in optoelectronics.

Luo et al. reported TiO₂ NRs arrays/Au-modulated V₂CT_x MXene-based self-powered UV PDs using an all-solution process technique. The wider bond-free surface of V₂CT_x MXene shows an increasing behavior, when it is in contact with Au (~5.35 eV) and suppresses the interface of the junction by reducing the charge carrier for facilitating hole transport. Eventually, at the UV illumination of 340 nm (65 mW/cm², 0 V), the responsivity, electron lifetime, dark saturation current density, and the detectivity of the PD are attained to be 28 mA/W, 8.95 μs, 2.06 × 10⁻² mA/cm², and 1.2 × 10¹¹ cmHz^{1/2}/W, respectively [214, 216]. The schematic representation of TiO₂ NR arrays/V₂CT_x

Fig. 8. (a) The schematic diagram of the device structure of SnO₂ NBS-based UV PDs; (b-d) Schematic representation of the sensing mechanism of PDs (b) under dark, (c) UV illumination, and (d) after turning off UV light; (e) I-V characteristics of PD under dark and UV light; (f) the EQE and responsivity are plotted with distinct concentration of NBS based UV PDs, Reproduced with permission @Elsevier[188]; (g) Schematic diagram of SnO₂/ZnO NBS based PD; (h) PL spectra of SnO₂/ZnO NBS; (i) The photocurrent vs time curve with the UV light on/off, Reproduced with permission @AIP [165]; (j) The schematic structure of the STNMAs/H₂O heterojunction-based UV PDs; (k) The energy band diagram and electron transfer mechanism for the STNMAs/H₂O heterojunction; (l) the photocurrent vs time curve under on/off radiation of 129 μW/cm² UV light, Reproduced with permission @springer link [189].

MXene-based UV PDs van der Waals (vdW) Schottky junction is reported (Fig. 9 e). The corresponding energy band diagram of the UV PDs vdW Schottky junction is also shown in Fig. 9 (f). The V₂CT_x MXene was not considered the transparent window layer in UV PDs but is frequently used for practical optoelectronic devices. Moreover, the device performance remains intact after 180 days of exposure to the atmosphere,

indicating the suitable durability and reliability of the machine, which benefited from the Au electrode covering the surface of V₂CT_x.

To fabricate TiO₂ NBS for the PEC detector, Lu et al. proposed a simple, facile, and cost-effective solution-based hydrothermal growth technique [215]. The manufactured device exhibited an excellent sensitivity of 114.8 μA/(ng.mL⁻¹) and a limit of detection (LOD) of

Table 3
Parameter comparison for different TiO₂ NSs-based UV PDs.

TiO ₂ NSs	Wavelength (nm)	Preparation techniques	Voltage (V)	Response time (s)	Responsivity (mA/W)	I _{photo} (μA)	Detectivity (Jones)	Ref.
0D NSs								
TiO ₂ nanocrystals	260	Sol-gel method	5	6	199	2.77	–	[201]
1D NSs								
TiO ₂ NWs	390	e-beam evaporation	5	120	6.85×10^{-2}	1.62×10^{-3}	–	[197]
2D NSs Thin films								
TiO ₂ TFs	365	Hydrothermal	5	17	13290	3.96	4.91×10^{13}	[202]
TiO ₂ film		ALD	0	0.5	69.2×10^{-3}	$\sim 10^{-5}$		[203]
In:TiO ₂ TFs	410	e-beam evaporation	6	–	–	152	–	[204]
Mg: TiO ₂ TFs	290	e-beam evaporation	3	0.13	18000		3×10^{12}	[205]
Er: TiO ₂ TFs	340	PVD	0.5	1.29	226	90×10^{-3}	8×10^{12}	[206]
TiO ₂ -PANI NFs	365	–	0.01	20	–	1.9	–	[207]
Nanoarray								
TiO ₂ NWs array	365	Hydrothermal	0	18	–	1.5×10^{-3}	–	[208]
TiO ₂ nanoarray		Hydrothermal	0	0.1	5×10^{-3}	–	–	[209]
TiO ₂ NRs	365	–	0.32	0.15	–	31	–	[90]
3D NSs								
Cr:TiO ₂ /ZnO NWs	373	Solgel and hydrothermal	5	–	250×10^3	14×10^3	–	[210]
TiO ₂ NWs/PANI NFs/ TiO ₂ NWs array	365	Hydrothermal and wet chemical deposition	0	1	–	8	–	[208]
NiO/TiO ₂ NRs	342	Hydrothermal	0	38.5	1.34×10^{-3}	0.3	–	[211]
NiO/TiO ₂ NRs/TiO _x	342	Hydrothermal	0	28.9	5.66×10^{-3}	0.4	–	[211]
TiO ₂ NRs/Au-V ₂ CT _x MXene	340	Etching and hydrothermal	0	0.17	28×10^{-3}	–	–	[212]
TiO ₂ /ZnO/Ag BNWs	380	–	–	1.10	730	–	–	[213]

26.3 ng.mL⁻¹, assisting a simple, label-free, rapid, sensitive, and noninvasive method to overcome the limitations of conventional techniques used for AD diagnosis. Fig. 9 (g) illustrates the distinct tailored morphology of TiO₂ NBs produced successfully using the hydrothermal method and conducting the PEC measurement under the illumination of a UV LED light source (~365 nm). Jiang et al. prepared mixed-dimensional TiO₂/ZnO/Ag core-shell NWs with brush-like structures for the potential of PEC PDs (Fig. 9 h and i). Under the broad UV (380 nm) to visible (420 nm) illumination, the device has achieved the high responsivity of 730 and 490 mA/W and low response (τ_r) /decay time (τ_d) of 1.10/0.91 sec and 1.52/0.61 sec, respectively. The underlying mechanism of PEC photoresponse can be expressed by using the following three aspects: (i) plasmonic light-matter interactions, (ii) type-II band alignment between TiO₂ and ZnO, and (iii) charge transfer processes across the TiO₂/ZnO/Ag NWs. Light trapping around TiO₂/ZnO-Ag interfaces for the LSPR effect occurs, enhancing the electric field and light absorption. Furthermore, these parameters significantly improve the PD's performance. This approach can fabricate mixed-dimensional heterostructures for high-performance optoelectronic devices. These parameters notably elevate the efficacy of PDs, showcasing the substantial capacity for producing high-performance optoelectronic devices with mixed-dimensional NB heterostructures [213].

3.4. Other metal oxides (MOx)

MOx have emerged as an up-and-coming class of materials for various technological applications owing to their unique properties, such as chemical stability, abundance, low cost, and high reactivity [217]. Despite the prominently used MOx (ZnO, TiO₂, and SnO₂), some other MOx, such as CuO or Cu₂O, NiO, V₂O₅, WO₃, and Co₃O₄, with distinct morphological structures, have emerged as desirable alternatives [218,219]. In particular, MOx-based NB morphologies are being developed using direct bandgap semiconductors with immense potential for UV PDs [27,220]. MOx are abundant, cost-effective, and non-toxic

and exhibit enormous stability, making them potential candidates for solar cells, solar water splitting (PEC), gas sensing, supercapacitors, lithium-ion batteries, PDs, and other photovoltaic devices. The MOx-based morphological NB development has opened up new opportunities for designing and fabricating high-performance and low-cost optoelectronic devices for various technological applications. These materials' exceptional properties and unique morphological structures make them preferred for distinct PDs. These materials hold great promise and have the potential to enable the development of innovative, high-performance solutions that could significantly benefit humanity.

Wang et al. reported the growth of branched ZnO NWs on CuO NWs and the fabricated p-CuO/n-ZnO heterojunction NSs-based PDs. Hydrothermally grown ZnO branched NWs were reasonably uniform, with an average length of 200 nm and diameter of 50 nm [221]. Under forward bias, it is reported that the voltage of the fabricated PD reduced from ~0.7 to ~0.2 V under UV illumination. The core-shell branched ZnO NWs on CuO NWs are layered on top of ITO/glass substrates, where transparently conductive substrate acts as the cathode and Cu core acts as an anode (Fig. 10 a). Fig. 10 (b) illustrates the energy bandgap of the prepared p-CuO/n-ZnO heterojunction at thermal equilibrium. The HAADF image of a p-CuO/n-ZnO heterojunction NBs and the corresponding EDX elemental mapping are shown in Fig. 10 (c) and (d), respectively.

Compared to the photoelectrode with a thin film structure, Shaismov et al. studied the PEC performance of CuO/ZnO-NBs PDs that significantly achieved the stability of the fabricated photoelectrode to be 82.13 % [222]. The performance of CuO/ZnO-NBs and film electrodes was estimated on behalf of several outcomes of distinct factors that begin from the NBs structure of the electrode (Fig. 10 e). The SEM images of the prepared nano heterostructure are significantly demonstrated in Fig. 10 (f) and (g). Using hydrothermal and chemical bath deposition techniques, Bai et al. synthesised the ZnO/Cu₂O branched heterojunction arrays to apply self-powered UV PDs. Under UV illumination, the PD exhibits a significant responsivity of 19 A/W and photocurrent 3 mA along with a rise time of 0.14 sec and decay time of

Fig. 9. (a) The schematic diagram of TiO₂ NBs array based UV PDs; (b) the growth mechanism of TiO₂ NBs array on FTO glass. (c) The electron transport mechanism in a TiO₂ NBs photoanode; (d) Time responses of photocurrents for PDs under UV light illumination at 0 V bias, Reproduced from permission @IOP [90]; (e) TiO₂ NR arrays/V₂CT_x MXene-based PD device; and (f) its energy band diagram, Reproduced from permission @Elsevier [214]; (g) PEC setup and detection mechanism, along with the growth process of TiO₂ NBs, Reproduced from permission @IEEE [215]; (h) The mechanism of TiO₂/ZnO/Ag core-shell NWs-based PDs; (i) FDTD simulation models of TiO₂/ZnO/Ag NWs with absorption spectra of TiO₂ NWs, TiO₂/ZnO NWs and TiO₂/ZnO/Ag core-shell NWs, Reproduced from permission @ACS [213].

Fig. 10. (a) The schematic structure of p-CuO/n-ZnO heterojunction NBs UV PDs; (b) The Energy band diagram of the CuO/n-ZnO NBs heterojunction describes the e-transport mechanism; (c) HAADF image taken from one single p-CuO/n-ZnO heterojunction NBs; (d) EDX elemental mappings of Cu, Reproduced from open access @IEEE [221]; (e) The schematic light absorption and charge transfer mechanism of CuO/ZnO-NR and CuO/ZnO film electrodes, Reproduced from open access @ACS [222]; (f-g) FE-SEM images of the CuO/ZnO photoelectrodes, Reproduced from open access @ACS [222]; (h) The energy band structure of Co₃O₄-ZnO NBs film; (i) Photocurrent v/s time plot of Co₃O₄-ZnO NBs film under UV illumination at zero bias condition; (j) single-cycle time response with photocurrent of the Co₃O₄-ZnO NBs, Reproduced with permission @ACS [164].

0.36 sec, respectively [91].

Wang et al. fabricated a stable, nontoxic, and low-cost self-powered Co₃O₄-ZnO bottlebrush NSs-based broadband PD. The prepared PDs had achieved improved responsivity (R) and specific detectivity (D) of 22.7 mA W⁻¹ and 3.14 × 10¹² Jones, respectively [164]. The schematic E-K diagram has described the functions of photoactive materials p-Co₃O₄ and n-ZnO after forming the pn-junction, as shown in Fig. 10 (h). Fig. 10 (i) illustrates the photocurrent of a Co₃O₄-ZnO NBs film subjected to UV light (360 nm), indicating stability after numerous switching cycles. The photocurrent was observed in the presence of UV light. Therefore, Co₃O₄-ZnO NBs films are highly responsive to UV light and can detect light signals in narrow bands. The time range (Fig. 10 j) provides a high response speed and a response/recovery time of 20/90 ms. Moreover, the self-powered PD device moves toward miniaturization, providing flexibility and portability. These innovative ideas are helpful in various photonics or optoelectronic applications (solar cells and photocatalysis) [164].

4. Photoresponse aspects in the MOx NBs based-UV PDs

Modern society’s perpetually developing future generations demand more sophisticated and effective technologies to implement in daily life and commercial applications. To accommodate the needs of future generations, researchers and scientists must develop UV PDs with extreme proficiency in quickly exhibiting extreme sensitivity and excellent at object recognition [223,224].

For specific photoactive materials, the device’s design will also overcome the challenges and limitations of PDs. The detection mechanisms of distinct MOx NBs-based UV PDs conclude that MOx with NBs morphology have higher response speed, responsivity, and photocurrent, which make them the most suitable for UV PDs. Apart from the designing and working mechanism of high-performance MOx-NBs UV PDs, the advanced device, including responsivity, detectivity, operating voltage, photocurrent, external quantum efficiency, photoconductive gain, response time, and stability, have been hypothesized, which is an

essential part of enhancing the absorption phenomenon and the photoelectric performance and expand their potential for on-field application.

The MOx NBs-based UV PDs have excellent photoresponse performance due to the extensive surface area of NBs, successful excitation of electron-hole pairs at the interface of heterojunction, higher quantum confinement, low junction potential, and the high mobility of NBs for collecting and transferring more carriers. The performance metrics are separated into two distinct groups: conventional and modern (Fig. 11). The traditional metrics comprise the fundamental parameters for improving the UV PDs' responsiveness, efficiency, and rapid response [225]. Meanwhile, modern performance metrics consider the demands of our modern society for electronic devices that are transparent, flexible, artificially intelligent, self-powered, and efficient under low illumination [226]. The MOx NBs-based UV PDs are characterized as improved high-performance UV PDs after enhancing these traditional and modern performance factors, as discussed below:

4.1. Photocurrent of UV PDs

Photocurrent of UV PDs was generated under UV illumination, which

is the unique current that distinguishes it from other currents [227]. The actual current of PDs can be estimated by subtracting the dark current from the photocurrent as given in the equation.

$$\Delta I = I_{light} - I_{dark} \tag{3}$$

where, I_{dark} and I_{light} are the currents in the absence and presence of UV light. The measured photocurrent could be explained using distinct parameters, including intensity, wavelength of illuminated light, and the characteristic morphologies of MOx. The typical graph between the photocurrent v/s time for demonstrating the significant surface recombination using Ag NWs/ZnO NRs under different light intensities (Fig. 12 a). Fig. 12 (b) explains the corresponding photocurrent of Co₃O₄-ZnO NBs film, Co₃O₄-ZnO NPs film, and Co₃O₄ NWs at the 0 V bias [164]. Under UV illumination (372 nm), the photocurrent response curve of a single CF/ZnO-CdS-based device is shown in Fig. 12 (c).

4.2. Responsivity

In the realm of UV PDs, responsivity, and detectivity are the fundamental phenomena that determine how they respond to incident optical power. These concepts refer to the ability of UV PDs to produce an

Fig. 11. The UV PD aspects of the conventional and latest metrics for enhanced detection, high S/N ratio, fast response, and high efficiency.

Fig. 12. (a) Photocurrent response curve of Ag NWs/ZnO NRs under distinct UV light intensity; (b) The photocurrent response curve compares $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{-ZnO}$ NBs film, $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{-ZnO}$ NPs film, and Co_3O_4 NWs at 0 bias; (c) The photocurrent response curve of a S-CF/ZnO-CdS based device under UV radiation; (d) The wavelength vs responsivity spectra at 1, 5, and 10 V bias voltages; (e) The photon responsivity derives at excitation intensity on the CF/ZnO-CdS NSs; (f) The spectral responses of fabricated p-CuO/n-ZnO heterojunction UV PDs; (g) The photocurrent and responsivity vs incidence intensity plotted on a logarithmic scale; (h) The linear relationship between light intensity and photocurrent and its responsivity of Ag NW@S-ZnO NR-based UV PDs; (i) The EQE and responsivity with precursor concentration of SnO_2 NB UV PDs; (j-k) The switching characteristics of UV PDs measured under dark and UV illumination with different Ag NWs/ZnO NRs weight ratios: (j) response time, (k) Sensitivity; (l) The photo responsivity and EQE of p-SC-SWNT/n-ZnO heterojunction device under UV illumination, Reproduced with permission @Elsevier, ACS, IEEE [67,129,130,188,221].

output signal, typically in the form of voltage or current, when exposed to incident UV radiation [228,229]. It is imperative to consider both the responsivity and detectivity of a UV detector as they increase with the photocurrent and provide vital information on the detector's sensitivity and performance. The responsivity (R) of the UV PD device can be expressed by using the following particular expression:

$$R = \frac{I_{\text{photo}}}{AP_{\text{UV}}} = \frac{I_{\text{light}} - I_{\text{dark}}}{AP} = \frac{ne}{h\nu} = \frac{n\lambda(\mu\text{m})}{1.24} (A/W) \quad (4)$$

Where, I_{light} and I_{dark} are the corresponding photo and dark currents, A is the UV signal exposed area, n is the number of the photon absorbed, λ is the wavelength of the incident radiation, ν is the frequency of the incident radiation, e is the charge on an electron (1.6×10^{-19} C), and P_{UV} is the UV power density, respectively.

The responsivity of UV PDs could be dignified through the various measurement graphs plotting the intensity or wavelength of the illuminated UV light. Fig. 12 (d) shows the responsivity spectra under a distinct bias voltage of 1, 5, and 10 V [129]. Fig. 12 (e) explains the relative photon responsivity derivate at an excitation intensity of CF/ZnO-CdS NSs. The measurement of the spectral responses of the fabricated p-CuO/n-ZnO heterojunction NSs UV PD device is shown in Fig. 12 (f). For the high responsivity of UV PDs, it is required to enhance the surface-to-volume ratio with distinct morphologies. These material properties increase the absorption of more photons, ultimately leading to increased responsivity. The standard 0-D NPs have shown lower responsivity. Meanwhile, 1-D/2-D nanostructures exhibit much higher responsivity, such as NRs, NTs, NWs (1-D), thin films, and nanoarrays (2-D).

Moreover, NWs are branched to form a brush-like morphology or the formation of proper NBs. They display the highest responsivity and detectivity due to their high surface-to-volume ratio. Additionally, the low junction potential and ease of electron flow from low to high work function of MOx until their Fermi levels reach equilibrium enhances the responsivity. Therefore, utilizing morphologies with a high surface-to-volume ratio can significantly increase the absorbed photon flux. This has significant implications for designing UV PDs, where the high responsivity is critical for particular scientific instruments or medical devices. The large surface area and effective light absorption of MOx NBs make them suitable materials for UV PDs. However, there is still scope for further development to enhance the efficiency of PDs in terms of their response speed. We summarize the following potential strategies to overcome this persistent challenge.

4.2.1. Material engineering

Reducing transit time and improving carrier mobility can be achieved by doping MOx with additional elements. When dopants are added to MOx, an impurity energy level forms, and the absorption edges move toward longer wavelengths resulting in elevated photocurrent [230]. Sol-gel deposited ZnO films with p-type conductivity were prepared by Dutta et al. using N doping and Al-N co-doping, respectively, the N-doped film performed better than the undoped and codoped films responding to UV radiation [231]. In-doped ZnO nanostructure, UV PD was evenly constructed by Young et al. on a glass substrate, which showed excellent oriented characteristics, a quick reaction time, and great sensitivity [232]. Doping-induced trap states generally have the potential to encourage charge carrier recombination, which would result in faster reaction times [27].

4.2.2. Device optimization

Time to respond can also be modified by optimizing the architecture of PDs by taking into account the factors that facilitate effective charge separation and collection, such as the active layer's thickness and doping, electrode geometry, the active region's thickness, and the formation of heterojunctions (junctions between various materials) [233–237]. Molina et al. synthesized a PD by depositing individual TiO₂ fibers onto pre-patterned Ti/Au electrodes on SiO₂/Si substrates, which had a quick reaction time of around 5 sec and a strong UV responsivity of 90 A W⁻¹ at 375 nm [238].

4.2.3. Plasmonic NPs

Localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) can be produced by depositing small metal NPs, such as Pt, Ag, or Au onto the surface of PDs, which focuses and amplifies incoming UV light. Therefore, more electron-hole pairs are formed increases the photocurrent and the response time of PDs [239]. Several plasmonic PDs that mix these plasmonic metal nanocrystals with low-dimensional MOx have shown exceptional plasmon-enhanced device performance by using the light-confinement effect and programmable light absorption [240–242]. Tian et al. deposited Pt NPs over MSM structured UV PDs, the responsivity of the PD increased from 0.836 to 1.306 A W⁻¹, indicating

increased photoelectric performance benefited by the LSPR effect of Pt NPs [243]. Guo et al. produced MgZnO MSM UV PDs and decorated the Pt NPs' surface. The surface plasmons of Pt NPs facilitated the improved scattering of incoming light, leading to a significant increase in the responsivity of all PDs with varying electrode spacing (3, 5, and 8 μm) [244].

4.2.4. 2D Van Der Waals heterostructures

2D vdW heterostructures with a smooth heterointerface, an adjustable bandgap, and ultrafast carrier transport account for the PDs' great sensitivity, substantial responsivity, and quick reaction time and rapid charge transfer are constrained in 2D [245–247]. Chen et al. fabricated a hybrid n-type 2D-layered MoSe₂/p-type MoOx vdW heterojunction PDs, which showed the rectifying response. Under 254 nm illumination (0.29 mWcm⁻²), the optimized device demonstrated the responsivity (3.4 A W⁻¹), detectivity (8.5×10⁷ Jones), and EQE (1665.6 %) at 5 V [248].

4.2.5. Built-in potential/ self-powered PD

The device's inherent potential can also affect the response time [249–251]. Zhao et al. developed a self-powered PD using a crystalline ZnO-Ga₂O₃ core-shell heterostructure microwire that exhibited a very high responsivity at 251 nm at 0 bias (9.7 mA W⁻¹), together with a rapid reaction speed (rise/decay durations of <100/900 μs), rendering it highly appropriate for self-powered photodetection in real-world applications [157]. Additionally, some new approaches have been investigated to enhance the self-power capabilities of PDs, such as the piezo-phototronic [252], thermo-phototronic [253,254], and photo-gating effects [255] for the connection between ferromagnetic electrodes and nanostructured materials [256].

4.3. Noise equivalent power (NEP)

NEP is the incident power applied to the PDs resulting in a unit signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the output for a certain frequency of modulation or rate of data-signalling, wavelength, and noise bandwidth. It can be expressed as responsivity as follows,

$$NEP = \frac{I_n}{R_i} = \frac{V_n}{R_v} \quad (5)$$

Where I_n , V_n are the current and voltage noises, respectively, and R_i , R_v is responsiveness analogous to current and voltage, respectively. As the noise voltage's root mean square (RMS) value is directly proportional to the bandwidth's square root, the NEP is also stated in the spectral density unit W/Hz^{1/2}. Hence the spectral sensitivity may be evaluated using NEP. For a particular PD, the lowest NEP (NEP_{min}) is attained at the wavelength when the PD's responsiveness is at its highest. Thus:

$$NEP(\lambda) = NEP_{\min} \frac{R(\max)}{R(\lambda)} \quad (6)$$

where $R(\max)$ is the maximum responsivity of the PDs and $R(\lambda)$ is the responsivity of the PDs at λ wavelength [257].

4.4. Detectivity and specific detectivity

The reciprocal of the Noise Equivalent Power (NEP) is known as the detectivity of PDs denoted by 'D'. The NEP is the lowest optical power that requires the PDs to produce a signal, that is comparable to its noise level. An increased value of D indicates a better ability of PDs to detect weak signals [258].

$$D = \frac{1}{NEP} \quad (7)$$

Various theoretical and practical investigations have demonstrated that the detectivity varies inversely with the square root of the active area of PDs [257].

$$DA_d^{1/2} = \text{const} \quad (8)$$

The specific detectivity is denoted by D^* , which is a normalized detectivity metric that takes the electrical bandwidth and active area of PDs into account and offers a common metric for evaluating the effectiveness of different PDs, regardless of their size or rate of operation. The square root of the product of the detector area and bandwidth is multiplied by the regular detectivity (D) to get D^* . A higher D^* value denotes a better-performing PD.

$$D^* = \frac{A \cdot BW^{1/2}}{NEP} \quad (9)$$

Where 'A' represents the area of PD (photosensitive region) and 'BW' represents the bandwidth of frequency. The specific detectivity is typically expressed in units of $\text{cmHz}^{1/2}/\text{W}$. The specific detectivity of PDs is influenced by material characteristics, device design, and operating wavelength [259].

4.5. Correction of Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of UV PDs

The sensitivity of UV PDs is a crucial factor related to the signal-to-noise (SNR) level upon exposure to UV light at a given intensity. The level of sensitivity or SNR depends on the energy of incident light, captured and the absorbance of the transmitted light, and also on the magnitude of the response current generated by the PD devices when exposed to UV light. Hence, it is essential to enhance both the response current and the sensitivity to ensure accurate, stable, and reliable detection of UV light [260]. The NB heterostructures provide a high surface-to-volume ratio, allowing the absorbance and capture of the large amount of transmitted light in the UV PDs. The branched brushes grow on NBs that capture a large amount of the transmitted light. It enhances the SNR, reducing the noise of UV PDs. The photo-to-dark current ratios (PDCRs) as a function of the applied bias voltages are related to the signal-to-noise ratio of the UV PDs and can be determined by the relation:

$$\text{PDCR} = \frac{I_l - I_d}{I_d} \quad (10)$$

where, I_l is the photocurrent at UV light illumination, and I_d is the dark current.

MOx NBs-based UV PDs are designed to generate a significant amount of photocurrent when exposed to UV light. MOx NBs have promising results in terms of their stability and photocurrent to improve the SNR of the device and detect UV light, making them suitable materials for developing UV PDs. The improved SNR of the device leads to better detection capabilities, making it a valuable tool in applications requiring particular and accurate UV light measurements.

4.6. Estimation of response speed of UV PDs

The response speed of a device is a vital component of its performance, particularly in applications such as optical communication and switching that require the quick tracking of rapidly changing optical signals. The rise and decay time are two essential metrics used to evaluate the response speed of a device. The rise time is required for the dark current to reach its peak current of $1 - e^{-1}$, while decay time is needed for the peak current to drop back to e^{-1} . The rise time (τ_r) is a critical parameter of the UV PDs that measures the response of a system to a stimulus or input signal. It is defined as the time interval taken by the UV PDs to increase the photocurrent signal from 0% to 90 % or its maximum value when exposed to the UV light.

$$\tau_r = t_{90\%} - t_{10\%} \quad (11)$$

where, $t_{10\%}$ and $t_{90\%}$ are the time at 10 % and 90 % of the saturation value.

The decay time (τ_d) measures the time that takes for the photocurrent signal to decrease to 10% of its initial value upon turning off the UV light source.

$$\tau_d = t_{10\%} - t_{90\%} \quad (12)$$

Where $t_{10\%}$ and $t_{90\%}$ are the times at 10 % and 90 % of the saturation value, respectively.

In the case of UV PDs, the photo-responsive speed plays a crucial role in determining the device's ability to respond to photon flux or electromagnetic signals. The rise time (τ_r) and decay time (τ_d) of the UV PDs are the primary metrics that quantify the photo-responsive speed of the device. These metrics provide a comprehensive understanding of the device's ability to detect and respond to UV radiation, which is essential in many applications such as environmental monitoring and biomedical imaging.

The photocurrent and responsivity versus incidence intensity for SnO₂ NBs UV PDs are plotted on a logarithmic scale, as shown in Fig. 12 (g). The linear relationship between light intensity and photocurrent and responsivity of Ag NW@S-ZnO NR UV PDs is shown in Fig. 12 (h) [129]. Fig. 12 (i) explains the EQE and responsivity with the distinct concentration of SnO₂ NB structured UV PDs. Correspondingly, the switching characteristics of UV PDs measured at 5 V bias under a dark environment and UV illumination (365 nm) with different Ag NWs/ZnO NRs weight ratios: the response time and sensitivity are summarised in Fig. 12 (j-k) [129]. The photo responsivity (black squares) and external quantum efficiency (blue triangles) of p-SC-SWNT/n-ZnO hetero-junction device as a function of incident 370 nm light intensity at a reverse bias of -2 V (Fig. 12l).

4.7. Thermal stability and other parameters

MOx NBs-based UV PDs have successfully achieved enhanced performance due to the brush-like morphology. However, there are still many essential aspects, particularly transparency, thermal strength, self-power, low illumination efficiency, and flexibility, that will help to build the next generation of electronics and optoelectronics [261]. UV PDs are electronic devices that convert UV light energy into electrical signals. They are widely used in various applications, such as flame detection, air quality monitoring, and biomedical imaging [262,263]. Traditional UV PDs require important energy to separate and transport photo carriers, resulting in internal heat generation, reducing the device's lifespan [226]. The self-powered UV PDs have been developed that offer an effective solution to energy-related issues by providing extremely low power consumption [261]. The self-powered MOx NBs-based UV PDs have several advantages, including a reduction in the overall size and mitigating unnecessary energy dissipation [225]. These devices exhibit faster photoconduction performance due to their high surface-to-volume ratio and quick separation and transportation of photogenerated electrons and holes through the internal built-in electric field under UV illumination [264]. The MOx NBs, such as ZnO, SnO₂, and TiO₂-based UV PDs, exhibit high thermal stability, making them suitable for operation in high-temperature environments.

The thermal stability is another crucial factor that directly impacts the durability of electronic devices [261]. The stability of UV PDs is significantly affected by the temperature due to strong surface states that result from their high surface-to-volume ratio. Flexible and transparent electronic devices have become increasingly important in developing next-generation optoelectronic applications, such as solar cells, image or video sensing, transparent displays, and space missile deflection systems [265,266]. These devices provide significant portability, wearability, foldability, and stretchability. They can also be compatible with various types of substrates, including plastics, paper, textiles, and curved/bio-surfaces [10]. Moreover, the UV PDs with a tree or brush-like nanoheterostructure exhibit high performance with great reliability even after being bent to a radius of several mm [267].

Therefore, these devices are suitable for applications that require flexibility and transparency, such as wearable devices and flexible displays [268].

4.8. Humidity

Humidity influences the photocurrent ratio, increases leakage current, and raises the dark current in MOx NBs-based UV PDs [269]. Variations in the sensitivity of the PDs may arise from the interaction of water molecules with the surface. The effect of humidity on UV PD performance can be described as,

4.8.1. Surface effects

Adsorption of water molecules onto the photodetector material might result in the formation of holes or electron traps. This may impede the flow of these charge carriers, lowering the sensitivity and reaction time of the photodetector. Excessive humidity levels can occasionally even cause leakage currents, which degrade the signal's overall quality [270].

4.8.2. Charge carrier behavior

Electron-hole pairs are produced in the PD material when UV light strikes it. Water molecules can trap these charge carriers in high humidity settings, which will impede their mobility and lower the total photocurrent that the detector generates [27].

4.8.3. Material characteristics

Some PDs materials are hygroscopic, which means that water vapor is easily absorbed by them. The material may enlarge as a result of this absorption, changing its optical characteristics and affecting light absorption. Furthermore, absorbed water molecules may occasionally take part in internal chemical processes that alter the material's electrical characteristics [271]. Device engineering and surface alterations, such as the creation of hydrophobic layers or the reduction of adsorption sites, can lessen the impacts of humidity [272]. Gaining an understanding of these principles can assist in enhancing the stability and performance of devices in real-world settings.

4.9. External quantum efficiency (EQE)

For every photon that strikes a photodetector, the probability of producing a charge carrier within the detector is known as quantum efficiency. The ratio of the number of photogenerated charge carriers, either photoelectrons or electron-hole pairs that contribute to the photocurrent to the number of input photons is known as the external quantum efficiency [273].

$$n_e = \frac{N}{S} \quad (13)$$

Where, n_e represents EQE, and N, S are the generated photoelectrons and input photons respectively. Subsequently, the incident optical power and photocurrent may be used to represent a detector's external quantum efficiency as [274].

$$n_e = \frac{i_{ph}/e}{P_s/h\nu} = \frac{h\nu i_{ph}}{eP_s} \quad (14)$$

The PD's spectrum response determines its quantum efficiency, which is contingent upon the incident photons' wavelength. The wavelength dependency of the ratio is described as the detector's responsivity below, which contributes to its wavelength dependence in addition to its explicit reliance on the optical frequency.

4.10. Bandwidth

The potential of PD responds to the light intensity referred to as the

bandwidth (B). It is the frequency range that detects and identifies the signal inside [275]. The most popular method for describing a PD bandwidth can be defined in terms of 3 dB. It is the frequency at which the detector's output power falls by 3 dB from its DC (zero frequency) value [276].

$$(f_{3DB}) = 0.886B = \frac{0.443}{T} \quad (15)$$

Where, T represents a rectangular time interval. The time takes for a step change in light intensity to cause the detector's output to increase from 10 % to 90 % of its final value, which is known as the rise time. The relationship between the rise time and related bandwidth is as follows [277]:

$$t_r = \frac{0.35}{f_{3DB}} \quad (16)$$

Where t_r is rise time and f_{3DB} is the 3-dB cutoff frequency. The Fourier transform of the impulse response or the registration of the detector's response at a single signal frequency at a time, while the sweeping signal frequency can be used to obtain the frequency response, which is defined as the frequency dependence of the responsivity $R(f)$ at a specific optical wavelength. The output current or voltage signal of a PD is characterized by its responsivity. The detector's output electrical power spectrum $R^2(f)$, which indicates a 3-dB bandwidth or cut-off frequency for a photodetector [278].

$$R^2(f_{3DB}) = \frac{1}{2}R^2(0) \quad (17)$$

The bandwidth is an important factor in estimating the performance of PD. Rapid oscillations in the light signal can be accurately captured by a photodetector with a large bandwidth for high-speed optical communications, where light pulses are used to transport data [279]. On the other hand, a detector with a small bandwidth may distort the signal, thus making the rapid transitions less clear and perhaps introducing mistakes. Intrinsic characteristics, such as carrier transit time and diffusion processes, in addition to the capacitance of the detector, affect the bandwidth of PDs. Trade-offs between features like responsivity and bandwidth are common in design considerations. Large bandwidth is prioritized in high-speed transmission, but maximum responsiveness is also kept on the priority for low-light detection. Various methods can be used to increase photodetector bandwidth, including the waveguides and other structures, decreasing the size of the active region, and employing specialist materials.

In summary, self-powered MOx NBs UV PDs offer an effective solution to energy-related issues in UV PDs. Table 4 summarises the characteristic performance parameters of distinct materials-based UV PDs. It has been concluded that NBs are the preferred microstructure due to the high surface-to-volume ratio and internal built-in electric field that provide faster photoconduction performance [27,280,281]. Their high thermal stability makes them suitable for operation in high-temperature environments. Flexible and transparent electronic devices with a tree or brush-like nanoheterostructure exhibit high performance with excellent reliability even after being bent, making them a promising candidate for next-generation optoelectronics [282].

5. Various in-field applications of MOx NBs-based UV PDs devices

The MOx NBs-based UV PDs have received attention as practical electronic devices for their revolutionary performance. Here, we introduce the next generation of solar cells (energy generation) and UV imaging that are the basis of future flexible, transparent, wearable or implantable smart devices.

Table 4

The comparison of characteristic performance parameters of distinct materials based on UV PDs in the literature.

Materials	λ (nm)	Preparation techniques	Voltage (V)	Response time (s)	Responsivity (A/W)	I_{photo} (μA)	EQE (%)	Ref.
GaAs Nanofilm	365	CVD and epitaxial lift-off technique	2	–	0.99	–	3.37×10^4	[283]
Graphene/ nanoporous GaN	360	–	1.5	0.35 ms	4.8×10^7	–	–	[284]
GaN-Ni/Si	–	Wet chemical etching and thermal cleaning	0	433 μs	2.47×10^3	–	1.35×10^4	[285]
Ta-doped n-Ga ₂ O ₃ / i-Ga ₂ O ₃ / p-GaN	220	Electron beam evaporation	0	0.086 ms	8.67	0.94	–	[286]
ZnO NPs film	–	Swelling controlled cracking method	2	15	2.2×10^7	0.201	7.5×10^9	[139]
ZnO NRs	365	Aqueous solution method	0.5	100	–	1.55	–	[145]
ZnO microrod	325	Vapor phase transport	5	6.28	4×10^4	45	–	[32]
ZnO nanotube	325	Wet-chemical reaction	0	900	0.0571	–	–	[146]
ZnS coated ZnO array	370	ACG method	0	42	–	202	–	[287]
ZnO NWs	365	CVD	5	590	0.5	280	160	[144]
Single ZnO NWs	365	Hydrothermal	2	11	2400	1.2	8.2×10^3	[128]
ZnO Nanodisk	365	Spin coating and Hydrothermal	3	15	3386	–	1.2×10^4	[150]
ZnO NW/CuSCN core-shell	370	Chemical bath deposition	2	3.48	0.02	51	–	[288]
ZnS/SnO ₂ core-shell ribbon	320	Thermal deposition, Photolithography	1	8	6.2×10^4	1.32	2.4×10^7	[192]
Co-doped ZnO	378	RF-magnetron sputtering technique	5	60	0.003	1.13	–	[289]
Hierarchical ZnO NBs	365	two-step hydrothermal method	–	0.235	10^4	–	8.2×10^3	[128]
Single Ag NW@ZnO NRs	365	two-step hydrothermal method	5	1	2.5	0.25 mA	–	[130]
Ag NW@ZnO NRs	365	two-step hydrothermal method	5	2.6	6.5×10^{-6}	$\sim 10^{-12}$ A	–	[129]
ZnO-CdS branched DS NW	372	facile two-step hydrothermal method	2	–	1.94×10^5	4.4	–	[67]
SiC/ZnO NBs	350	Hydrothermal and carbonization process	1	0.040	4.8×10^5	18 nA	1.69×10^8	[134]
Thorn-like ZnO-MWCNT NSs	375	ALD and hydrothermal method	5	0.029	45.1	0.013 A	14927	[135]
ZnO/Cu ₂ O-NB	–	Hydrothermal & chemical deposition	–	0.14	–	19.3 mA	–	[91]
CO ₃ O ₄ -ZnO NBs film	360	two-step hydrothermal method	0	0.020	80.3×10^{-3}	0.68 mA	–	[164]
SnO ₂ /ZnO hierarchical NBs	365	Hydrothermal	5	0.622	–	40	–	[165]
NiO/TiO ₂ NRs	342	Hydrothermal	0	38.5	1.34×10^{-3}	0.3	–	[211]
NiO/TiO ₂ NRs/TiO _x	342	Hydrothermal	0	28.9	5.66×10^{-3}	0.4	–	[211]
TiO ₂ nanocrystals	260	Sol-gel method	5	6	199	2.77	–	[201]
TiO ₂ NRs/Au-V ₂ CT _x MXene	340	Etching and hydrothermal	0	0.17	28×10^{-3}	–	–	[212]
TiO ₂ film	–	ALD	0	0.5	69.2×10^{-3}	$\sim 10^{-5}$	–	[203]
TiO ₂ nanoarray	–	Hydrothermal	0	0.1	5×10^{-3}	–	–	[209]
SnO ₂ NWs	320	VLS process	1	50	–	2.1	1.32×10^7	[290]
SnO ₂ Nanonets	320	oil-water interfacial self-assembly	1	50	–	232	–	[291]
ZnO/SnO ₂ nanofibers	300	Hydrothermal	10	32.2	–	1.7×10^{-12}	–	[292]
SnO ₂ Nanobranches	375	Hot wall nebulizer & spray pyrolysis	0.0004	250	15×10^{-3}	0.00143	–	[188]
TiO ₂ /SnO ₂ B-heterojunction NSs	330	Electrospinning and drop drying method	–	0.03	0.6	–	–	[293]

5.1. Structured NBs for dye-sensitized solar cells

DSSCs appeared among the leading options for next-generation energy harvesting systems due to the ease of specific benefits for production, affordability, and adaptable aesthetic characteristics [294,295]. The development of DSSCs has become more efficient in recent years due to every element, including dyes, photoanodes, electrolyte additives, and counter electrodes. The potential of MOx-NBs can enhance the light-harvesting capabilities [296,297]. These MOx-NBs offer several advantages, including increased absorption and scattering of light [298]. Shao et al. prepared forest-like TiO₂ hierarchical structures using the acid-assisted hydrothermal method without any template or additive. Compared to NR array films, the performance of dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) constructed with NB structures was enhanced significantly [299]. The schematic growth process of the forest-like hierarchical structures on Ti plates (Fig. 13 a) and on FTO (Fig. 13 b) are tabulated. The transportation mechanism of the presumed preferential electron pathway in the hierarchical NBs photoanodes is described (Fig. 13 c,d). Additionally The NBs morphology provides a longer path to travel light through the absorbing layer, using the same amount of material as a conventional planar device [300]. The schematic illustration demonstrates the advantageous vertical NBs' over vertical NWs and planar solar energy conversion devices (Fig. 13e-h). The planar devices have thick junction potential enough to absorb incident light, which is the restriction by limiting the minority carrier diffusion lengths (Fig. 13e).

NWs have a long axis for the incident light absorption and, orthogonally, a short radial axis to separate charge, accommodating lower quality materials (Fig. 13f).

NBs have increased the light scattering characteristics and photo carrier generation (Fig. 13g). Fig. 13(h) illustrates the bandgap structure mechanism of NBs heterostructures with well-controlled electronic structures for improving solar energy harvesting [30,304]. Hierarchical NBs are efficient light scatterers, increasing interaction between the material and incident light, improving photon localization in the anode and enhancing light-harvesting efficiency [305]. Therefore, it is evident that 3D NSs are practical for efficient solar cells and an up-and-coming solution for improving solar energy conversion [306]. These extensively branched structures with vast surface areas effectively capture solar light like trees exposed to large surfaces for efficient photosynthesis. Compared to thin films, simple silicon NWs can reduce the light reflection by one to two orders of magnitude across the 300–1100 nm spectrum [307].

Pawar et al. utilized a cost-effective and low-temperature aqueous chemical method to grow 3D ZnO bottle brush-like morphology on conducting glass substrates (FTO) as a photoanode of DSSCs. This method involved chemicals to modify the FTO surface precisely, leading to improved conductivity and other beneficial properties [301]. The J-V characteristics for ZnO NR and ZnO NB films are compared (Fig. 12 i). Compared to aligned NRs, the grown bottle brush-like NS enables a 43 % increase in solar energy conversion efficiency. The branched NSs

Fig. 13. (a–b) Schematically grown forest-like hierarchical photoanodes (a) on Ti plates and (b) on the FTO substrates; (c) the schematic electron transfer mechanism of the hierarchical photoanodes, Reproduced with permission @ACS [299]; (d) The electron transport mechanism in a DSSC photoanode based on TiO₂ NBs arrays; (e–g) Schematic illustration demonstrating the electron transport mechanism in (e) planar devices, (f) vertical NWs, and (g) vertical NBs for solar energy conversion devices; (h) The bandgap structure of NBs heterostructures for improving solar energy harvesting, Reproduce from open access @RSC [300]; (i) J–V characteristics for ZnO NRs and ZnO NB films, Reproduced with permission @Elsevier [301]; (j) J–V curves for DSSC made from NRs and NBs structures grown using lower and doubled citrate, Reproduce from open access @RSC [302]; (k) J–V curves of DSSCs assembled using rutile TiO₂ NRs and rutile-anatase TiO₂ NBs arrays as photoanodes, Reproduce with permission @Elsevier [303].

significantly improved both light scattering and dye molecule adsorption. Moreover, the most effective way of harvesting light is to increase the effectiveness of solar cells.

Pace et al. demonstrated that brush-like ZnO NSs are an alternative to DSSC photoanode to enhance the performance. The J_{SC} was observed to be $7.97 \pm 0.03 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ and PCE of $\sim 1.95 \pm 0.03 \%$ respectively. The highest efficiency still falls below 2%, whereas analogous dye-electrolyte systems, combined with mesoporous TiO₂ photoanodes accomplished efficiencies of up to 10% [302]. The current density of NBs (red line) was observed to be better than that of NRs (black line) (Fig. 13 j). It is concluded that NBs-based PDs are comparatively better photoanodes of DSSCs due to increasing the surface area exposed to light irradiation.

Kwon et al. prepared rutile-anatase TiO₂ NB arrays using two-step hydrothermal-synthesis methods that achieved the efficiency of DSSCs to be 3.45% [303]. The current density v/s potential difference of DSSCs assembled of rutile TiO₂ NRs and rutile-anatase TiO₂ NBs arrays as photoanodes (Fig. 13 k). Wang et al. successfully developed the rutile TiO₂ NB arrays on FTO using a two-step wet chemical synthesis process. In their study of the PEC properties of the films for DSSCs, they discovered that using 3 mm long rutile TiO₂ NBs arrays as the

photoanode in the DSSCs resulted in a remarkable light-to-electricity conversion efficiency of 3.75% [308]. This efficiency is nearly three times higher than bare NR arrays, thanks to the increased dye adsorption and light harvesting efficiency, while maintaining excellent electron conductivity similar to vertical NRs.

Oh et al. synthesized TiO₂ branched NSs photoelectrodes for DSSCs by the seeding method, but the 1D NSs still lay in the plane of the FTO. The synthesized photoelectrodes reported short-circuiting current density of TiO₂-NW and TiO₂-NB increased from 6.25 to 12.18 mA/cm², and cell efficiency increased from 2.6% to 4.3%, respectively, due to increasing specific surface area and roughness [309].

Hara et al. fabricated a Ta-doped TiO₂ brush-like structure on P-ITO and fluorinated SnO₂ (FTO) substrates using nanoimprint lithography and pulsed laser deposition (PLD). The film of Ta:TiO₂ grew vertically and separately on the P-ITO and formed a brush-like structure. The device performance has been achieved with sheet resistance 15.6 Ω/square, short circuit current density (J_{SC}) 10.3 mA/cm², efficiency 3.2%, fill factor (FF) 0.51, and V_{oc} 0.6 V under the 600–750 nm range [310]. Introducing a blocking layer on the P-ITO substrate can significantly optimize the device performance and improve FF. However, the Ta:TiO₂ film's open brush-like structure could enable better infiltration

of ionic polymers or small molecule hole conductors for solid-state DSSCs and other optoelectronic applications. Feng et al. synthesized the vertically aligned hierarchical TiO₂ NW/ZnO NR hybrid arrays as an excellent photoanode candidate for superior light utilization. The prepared device illustrates improved performance, shaving current density of 12.49 mA cm⁻² and an efficiency of 3.20 %, along with the form factor (FF) of 0.52, respectively[311].

5.2. NBs for photoelectrochemical (PEC) cells

MOx-based NBs morphologies increasingly garner interest for their potential in PEC water-splitting applications due to their strong oxidation power, chemical stability, non-toxicity, and low production costs [312,313]. However, the significant energy bandgap of MOx has hindered the PEC water-splitting performance of unmodified MOx-based

NB electrodes[314]. Typically, only UV solar energy can be harnessed, which curtails the STH conversion efficiency of MOx[315,316]. Bandgap engineering, visible-light-absorbing sensitizers, and plasmon resonance energy transfer (PRET) have been exploited to prepare practical PEC MOx-based NBs[317–319]. The application of PEC systems based on photoactive semiconducting electrodes to the problem of solar energy conversion and chemical synthesis is discussed[320].

Kim et al. fabricated CuO/ZnO photoelectrodes and investigated the PEC performance and properties, respectively. The experiments conclude by showing superior PEC properties compared to the photoelectrodes with thin film NSs and also exhibit 82.13 % better stability in the PEC conditions. The schematic illustration of the PEC cell having efficient ZnO NBs photoelectrodes under sunlight (Fig. 14 a). Based on the EIS circuit analysis results, Fig. 14 (b) shows the schematic illustration of the electron transfer kinetics in the ZnO NB microstructures.

Fig. 14. (a) Schematic illustration of the PEC cell having efficient ZnO NBs photoelectrodes; (b) Systematic electron-hole transfer kinetics of ZnO NBs under illumination; (c) Suggested band alignments under dark equilibrium, bias and illumination, Reproduced with permission @Elsevier [321]; (d) Schematic illustration of the formation of the p-n junction between p-CuO and n-ZnO; (e) Schematic illustration of the CuO NR trunk and ZnO NR along the NBs; (f) The PEC measurements of the prepared electrodes, Reproduced with permission @Elsevier [322]; (g) Schematic of working mechanism of the PEC device with Au TNPs/ rGO/TiO₂ b-NRs photoelectrodes under sunlight; (h) Schematic of charge transfer mechanism for the Au TNPs/ rGO/TiO₂ system under the UV light and visible light illumination; (i) Photocurrent density collected with three chopped light on-off cycles at 0.5 V, Reproduced with permission @ACS [323].

Considering ZnO NB's overgrown NBs constitute an extensive photo inactive region, the slow rate of electron transfer from NBs to NRs backbones suggested by the material's high charge recombination and inadequate carrier fabrication means delayed kinetics. The band structures for the light-activated states of ZnO NBs were estimated by moving the Fermi levels of the band structures in (i) the dark state, (ii) dark activated or bias state and (iii) the illumination state for the photo potential analysis (Fig. 14 c). Furthermore, the photogenerated charge carriers contribute to some degree of Fermi-level recovery for each sample under illumination, SCR shrinkage and a reduction in band bending[321].

Shaislamov et al. CuO/ZnO NR-NBs photocathode as a PEC hydrogen generation. The fabricated p-CuO/ZnO NR-NBs photoelectrodes exhibited enhanced electrochemical stability, which is highly advantageous and can also be used for other unstable MOx semiconductor-based electrodes[322]. The p-CuO and n-ZnO heterojunction in contact with an electrolyte at a thermal equilibrium state is schematically illustrated (Fig. 14 d). When a light with more remarkable photon energy than their bandgap is shown on these semiconductors, excited electrons in the VB move to the CB of CuO and ZnO, creating holes in the VB. The photo-generated electrons then transfer from the CB of CuO to the CB of ZnO, facilitated by a favourable potential difference between them, and participate in a red/ox reaction at the ZnO/electrolyte interface.

Moreover, the holes move from the VB of ZnO to the VB of CuO and are further transferred to the counter electrode through the electrode back contact, effectively separating the photogenerated charges[324, 325]. The schematic illustration of the CuO NR trunk and ZnO NR along with the NBs is shown in Fig. 14 (e). The photocurrent vs time measurements were performed at a fixed bias of 0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl for an extended period (Fig. 14 f).

Ho et al. confidently prepared 3-D TiO₂-branched NR arrays in combination with plasmonic Au triangular NPs and r-GO sheets to apply PEC water oxidation. The prepared photoelectrodes exhibited up to 91 % of the enhancements at 5 V, respectively[323]. The schematic of the working mechanism of the PEC device with Au TNPs/erGO/TiO₂ branched-NRs photoelectrodes under sunlight is shown in Fig. 14 (g). The electron-hole pairs are immediately photogenerated in TiO₂, and the electrons in the conduction band could be either transferred directly to the underneath FTO substrate or accepted by the r-GO under UV light illumination and visible light irradiation (Fig. 14 h). The photocurrent response was tested using three consecutive cycles of on-and-off description at 0.5 V (Fig. 14 i). It was clear that the photocurrent values were relatively steady throughout the experiments and that the recorded photocurrent densities essentially agreed with the results of the LSV measurements.

Ning et al. obtained TiO₂ nanotree array films on the FTO substrates using the facile two-step hydrothermal method. Furthermore, the branches achieved enormous surfaces and flaws that served as trapping sites for unexpected charge recombination, strengthening the barrier to electron transport and decreased the current density[326].

5.3. NBs for additional practical aspects

The MOx NBs-based UV PDs have numerous practical applications due to their enhanced functional sites. UV sensors, including the photoelectrochemical cell, visible-blind image sensors, and so on were used to detect UV radiation[327]. Flexible devices are integrated with wearable systems that provide real-time UV exposure monitoring. They have been used in solar cells for power generation, enabling higher efficiency and lower manufacturing costs.

MOx NBs are appropriate for a variety of imaging applications and can provide a broad range of UV-detecting wavelengths to detect weak UV signals because of their great sensitivity, and quick response [328]. The wide and very uniform surface area provided by NB structures ensures a constant response across the PD device, which is vital for recording images free of flaws and irregularities[165]. Owing to the

exceptional chemical and thermal stability, MOx NBs-based UV PDs are less vulnerable to external variables' deterioration, guaranteeing dependable performance over an extended amount of time [1]. Furthermore, to effectively convert the photocurrent produced by the PD into a digital signal, MOx-based NBs are integrated with readout chips resulting in low-power consumption and miniaturised UV-PD design [328]. Due to such unique properties, readout chips integrated MOx NBs-based UV PDs are a promising technology for detection in security and surveillance, machine vision (industrial automation), scientific imaging, astronomy and space science including the following specialized imaging applications [329].

5.3.1. Medical imaging

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), and X-ray imaging are among the medical imaging modalities that use PDs with readout chips[330]. For diagnosis and treatment, these systems can detect and interpret the signals from radiofrequency to X-rays to produce precise anatomical and functional images. For biomedical imaging, bioluminescence, fluorescence, and confocal microscopy are used PDs with readout chips. With the use of these systems, biological materials labeled with certain probes or reporters can produce fluorescent or luminescent signals that can be used to visualize cellular architecture, molecular interactions, and physiological processes with extreme sensitivity and resolution[331, 332].

5.3.2. Thermal and LIDAR imaging

Infrared (IR) radiation-sensitive PDs are paired with readout circuits specifically designed for IR detection in thermal imaging systems [333–335]. These devices identify thermal signatures released by things or live things, opening up new uses in industrial inspection, surveillance, night vision, and medical diagnostics. For 3D imaging and distant sensing applications, light detection and ranging (LIDAR) systems use PDs with integrated readout circuits[336]. For forestry, urban planning, and autonomous navigation, LIDAR systems use laser pulses to record the duration of flight of the reflected light through PDs and readout chips. This allows for the creation of high-resolution 3D maps of the terrain, buildings, and objects[337,338]. MOx NBs-based UV PDs with readout chips are ideal for thermal sensing because of their quick reaction times, for developing very sensitive and quick-reacting flame sensors[337].

5.3.3. Remote environmental monitoring

Digital cameras' primary components are PDs with built-in readout chips. High-resolution, dynamic, and color-accurate digital images are produced by utilizing PDs to detect light photons, converting them to electronic signals, and processing them with readout chips[339]. In remote sensing applications, PDs incorporating readout chips are used for agricultural assessment, environmental monitoring, and earth observation. To research the landscape, vegetative health, and environmental changes, these devices take multispectral or hyperspectral photographs of the earth's surface by sensing light emitted or reflected by various materials[340,341]. For video surveillance, motion detection, and intrusion detection are equipped with PDs with readout chips. These systems provide for continuous surveillance, detection of threats, and recording of events in public areas, transit hubs, and vital infrastructure facilities. They accomplish this by capturing and processing images in a variety of lighting conditions[342]. Miniaturized and portable MOx NBs-based UV PDs with readout chips are useful for monitoring or evaluating environmental issues like air and water quality [340].

5.3.4. Characterization of materials

UV reflectance spectroscopy studies the properties of surface material and thin films[343]. Kohlmann et al. grown ZnO NBs on ZnO micro-tetrapods using the self-patterned preferential etching technique

in an H_2 -acetylene plasma. These core-shell ZnO NBs had exceptional sensitivity, indicating their ability to detect even the slightest changes in the environment. Furthermore, the NBs displayed impressive selectivity, allowing them to accurately distinguish between other analytes [77]. The response time of the fabricated NBs was reported to be as fast as 15 sec, while the recovery time was only 6 sec, making them highly efficient in practical applications. Overall, the NBs-based findings suggest that ZnO NBs could be a promising sensor option due to their high sensitivity, selectivity, and quick response time.

In their scientific investigation, Rakshit et al. prepared brush-like SnO_2 NWs/ZnO NRs, which possess a unique nanoheterostructure utilizing a combination of PLD and hydrothermal methods [344]. The researchers comprehensively analysed the sensing performance of these nano-heterostructures for various volatile organic compounds (VOCs), including triethylamine, toluene, ethanol, acetic acid, acetone, and methanol. Moreover, the brush-like SnO_2 NWs/ZnO NRs can be used as high-performance sensing materials for detecting a wide range of VOCs in various applications. Cao et al. successfully fabricated pine branches like SnO_2/ZnO nanoheterostructured PDs, which is a promising candidate for visible-blind image sensors. The SnO_2/ZnO PDs also exhibit fast response speed with a rising time of 0.48 ms and decay time of 2.07 ms, which exceeds most MO_x -based PDs [345]. The fabrication approach of pine-branch-like heterojunction can be extended to other 1D materials for high-performance optoelectronic devices (Fig. 15 a). The band structural mechanism (Fig. 15 b) explains the ease of electron transport due to the nanoheterostructural design. The current vs time plots were examined to know the enhancement in the device performance under different light power densities. The PD current of the prepared sample increases with increasing light power density (Fig. 15 c).

Wang et al. synthesized the hierarchical TiO_2 NBs arrays using a simple hydrothermal method for UV sensing of PECs [346]. These novel NS arrays provide efficient transport networks and a large interface area, resulting in a high responsivity of 0.11 A/W, a fast response time of

20–40 ms for current signal, and a self-powered visible-blind UV sensor with considerable spectral response under weak irradiation (Fig. 15 d). The photocurrent switching behaviour and time sensitivity of devices under 25 mWcm^{-2} at 365 nm are illustrated in Fig. 15 (e). Moreover, this study offers a simple and effective strategy for improving the performance of PEC-UV sensors.

Moreover, the MO_x NBs-based UV PDs allow distinct factories to detect their product appearance features and spatial position. This innovative technology can also monitor other applications' production processes, leading to more efficient assembly lines and increased productivity. With the ability to recognize or track products throughout the manufacturing process, these UV PDs can be implemented to develop intelligent and unmanned monitoring. Overall, these devices hold enormous use and exploration of their capabilities is highly recommended.

6. Challenges and limitations of NBs-based UV PDs

MO_x NBs-based UV PDs have undergone significant advancements, particularly in terms of rapid response time and speed. Several challenges need to be addressed to expand the study of their performance and in-field applications. An ideal UV PD should exhibit excellent thermal and optical stabilities, high on/off photocurrent ratio, fast response time, and high sensitivity while being self-powered and having low energy consumption [347]. Self-powered UV PDs are still in the early stages of development, and the deposition of the material only into the selected regions for NB growth presents a challenge. The morphology of the NBs is affected by various factors, including the etching solution and corrosion time, which can impede the bridging process. High-temperature processing has several limitations, such as impurities in the final product and the use of vacuum conditions that hinder the larger-scale production of these materials. Without damaging the existing prefabricated structure or hindering their functions,

Fig. 15. (a) Schematic illustration of the light trap and absorption phenomenon of SnO_2/ZnO UV PDs; (b) The band structural mechanism of SnO_2/ZnO UV PDs; (c) Current-time curves of SnO_2/ZnO PDs under 300 nm light irradiation and at different light intensities, Reproduced with permission @Wiley [345]; (d) The light absorbing and trapping of charge carriers of TiO_2 NBs arrays PEC UV sensor; (e) The J-T curve defining the photocurrent switching behaviour, Reproduced with permission @Elsevier [346].

development of these NB-based devices in any post-processing operations is a major challenge. ZnO-based UV PDs, in particular, suffer from long rise/fall time leading to lower responsivity and detectivity. To realize the full potential of MOx NBs-based UV PDs, a simple and cost-effective process for their preparation needs to be developed. Novel techniques are required to be explored to overcome the challenges associated with self-powered UV PDs and the deposition of material for NB growth. The influence of various factors on the NB morphology needs to be studied in detail to optimize the process[348]. Further research is essential to overcome these limitations of high-temperature processing to develop new techniques for synthesizing NBs that do not damage existing prefabricated devices.

7. Future perspective and outlook

Core-shell MOx-based NBs with unique morphological structures could be an ideal photoactive material for advanced self-powered UV PDs with high selectivity and sensitivity. The high surface-to-volume ratio, low-junction potential, quantum confinement, and ease of electron transfer have significantly impacted the field of fast-response UV PDs. Despite these developments, there is still need to explore new concepts of UV PDs offering more flexibility, transparency, portability, wearability, and real-time capabilities to broaden their scopes. Thereby, it provides greater convenience to daily life and industrial productions. For example, the flexibility aspect of MOx NBs-based UV PDs is an exciting area of exploration. It would allow for the creation of conformable sensors that can be integrated into wearable devices, enabling real-time monitoring of UV exposure. Additionally, the transparency aspect of these UV PDs makes them well-suited for integration into windows, windshields, and other glass surfaces, enabling real-time monitoring of UV exposure in indoor environments. Overall, MOx NBs-based UV PDs hold enormous potential for the future, and further exploration of their performance aspects and in-field applications is highly recommended (Fig. 16).

The response speed of MOx-based UV PD devices measures the ability to track rapidly changing optical signals, which is a critical issue for applications of optical communication/imaging/detection. NWs are further branched to form a brush-like morphology (NBs) that exhibit the highest response speed, allowing a high surface-to-volume ratio and ease of electron flow from low to high work function until their Fermi levels reach in equilibrium. The response speed can be further enhanced using several post-treatment processes, including temperature ambient operations, functionalization, and high-energy irradiation. NBs-based UV PDs enhanced the responsivity and response speed for significant absorption of the photon flux, resulting in high photo-responsiveness of PDs. Numerous approaches exist to further enhancing the responsivity of NBs, including the periodic growth, implementation of an anodizing profile, manipulating the carbon concentration across the branches of NBs, encapsulation or functionalization of noble metals, and the utilization of high-energy irradiation. With the pursuit of high sensitivities, response speed, and stabilities, the MOx NBs-based UV PDs have been developed to recognize and monitor flames from various sources, including forest fires, missiles, fighter jets, and aircraft. These explicit features are vital in many practical applications, such as forest fire warning and national defence.

This article summarises MOx NBs-based UV PDs that vary by concerning the microstructure or the core-shell nanostructure to revolutionize modern lifestyles including MEMS (Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems), healthcare, chemical analysis, environmental monitoring, aerospace and many more by offering compact, efficient, and versatile solutions for monitoring, diagnosis, and treatment in various medical scenarios. Some latest advancements and potential applications of miniaturized photodetectors in the modern world include.

7.1. Advances in MEMS and IOT devices

The integration of MOx NBs-based UV PDs technology is expected to have a significant impact on the development of MEMS, IoT devices and

Fig. 16. The versatile MOx NBs-based UV PDs are employed in various in-field applications, including air quality monitoring, medical diagnosis, PV power generation and so on.

optoelectronics. This advancement has the potential to enhance the ruggedness and portability of optical sensing technologies, making them more reliable and efficient in various applications. Utilization of MOx NBs-based UV PD technology would enable to the development of more advanced/sophisticated optical sensing systems, which can be used in a wide range of industries particularly for medical, automotive, aerospace, and many more.

7.2. Chemical analysis and spectroscopy

MOx NBs-based UV PDs would be used for sensitive chemical analysis and spectroscopy, which is a valuable in diagnosing and monitoring certain respiratory conditions. These PDs would also be capable in low-level chemical detection and analysis, making them ideal for monitoring patients. Additionally, these PDs offer the convenience of home healthcare self-monitoring, saving patients time and money.

7.3. Blood-oxygen measurement

MOx NBs-based UV PDs would have great potential for the development of lightweight and conformal wrist bands for blood-oxygen measurements. These innovative devices enable continuous monitoring of oxygen levels in patients and will be particularly useful in situations where traditional bulky devices are not practical or convenient. With their compact size and high accuracy, MOx NBs-based UV PDs would offer a promising solution for non-invasive and comfortable monitoring of blood oxygen saturation levels in real time.

7.4. Biological Sensing

MOx NBs-based UV PD technology can be used in a wide range of biological sensing applications. These devices would be highly sensitive that detect specific biomarkers with great accuracy, making them invaluable tools for medical research and diagnostics. They could also be used to monitor physiological parameters, such as heart rate and blood pressure in real time, providing clinicians with valuable insights into their patients' health. In addition, MOx NBs-based UV PDs are highly portable and easy to use, making them ideal for point-of-care (PoC) diagnostics in healthcare settings. Overall, this technology has the potential to revolutionize in the field of medical diagnostics and improve patient outcomes.

7.5. Environmental measurements

The MOx NBs-based UV PDs can also be used in monitoring complex environment, which is of paramount importance. Whereas, the traditional UV PDs with a single function may not be sufficient to detect changes in various environmental signals. The MOx NBs can detect multiple environmental signals simultaneously, making them highly effective and efficient tools that can leverage triboelectric, optoelectronics, piezo-phototronic, and piezo-resistive applications.

Moreover, the development of multifunctional MOx NBs-based UV PDs represents a significant advancement in UV PD technology. By harnessing the power of technology, we can make our world safer and contribute to a better future to all. The unwavering dedication to optimizing MOx-based-UV PDs for enhanced responsiveness is rapidly becoming the norm. Moving forward, the development of these devices will undoubtedly be influenced by their specific application fields. With simultaneous advancements in multiple areas, the future of these PDs looks incredibly promising.

8. Summary and conclusion

MOx NBs-based UV PD is an outstanding innovation in the field of UV detection systems, that is the most promising device of recent times for pollution monitoring, energy harvesting, security systems, medical,

and communications. MOx NBs can be grown by encapsulating 1D MOx on other 1D NSs enhanced functionalities for UV PDs offering better sensitivity, quick response, and high responsivity. A brief description for the growth of NBs and the detection mechanism of UV PDs is presented for the latest generation aspects, such as flexibility, transparency, wearability, AI smartness, advanced efficiency, multifunctionality, and self-powering. The two-step growth hydrothermal technique creates tunable surface morphological NBs with high surface area, robust mechanical and thermal endurance, high mechanical stability, and flexibility. This review explores the growth mechanism and detection performance of MOx NBs due to ease and low-cost manufacturing with distinctive brush-like morphologies. The average response time of NBs-based UV PDs is highly recommended for detection in the microseconds (μ s) to milliseconds (ms) range. Compared to standard microstructure-based UV PDs (NPs (0-D), NRs, NTs, NWs (1-D), nanoarray (2-D) and thin films), NBs-based UV PDs can offer the enhancement in light absorption, photoreponse, mechanical flexibility, and stability that makes them a promising candidates for advanced PD applications. Moreover, their brush-like morphology exhibits the highest response speed due to the high surface-to-volume ratio and ease of electron flow with reduced traps. Post-treatment techniques (ambient treatment, functionalizing, and high-energy irradiation) can further enhance the response speed of UV PDs. These high-speed PD devices could also be utilized as an indispensable tool for laser and photonics research by further structural or surface modification, including anodizing and doping, where distinct noble metals and structural carbonaceous nanomaterials are substituted in the structure of the prepared nanoheterostructure. These MOx NBs-based UV PDs are best suited for ultrafast PDs and optoelectronic devices featuring rise times as short as a few nanoseconds (ns) to picoseconds (ps).

The flexibility aspect of MOx NBs-based UV PDs is another exciting area of exploration, as it would allow for the creation of conformable sensors that can be integrated into wearable devices, enabling real-time monitoring of UV exposure. Additionally, the transparency aspect of these UV PDs makes them well-suited for integration into windows, windshields, and other glass surfaces, enabling real-time monitoring of UV exposure in indoor environments. The detailed discussion on UV PD devices' advancements and challenges will provide the scientific society with innovative ideas to achieve sustainable development goals. This review unlocks the incredible potential of NBs UV PDs to the scientific community and production industries by improving the performance aspects. This includes enhancing the responsivity, specific-detectivity, external quantum efficiency, and response time for applications of PV power generation, optical communications, security, gas detection, motion detection, biomedical imaging, and video imaging. By pursuing these improvements, we can release the enormous potential of MOx NBs-based UV PDs for their in-field and fastest real-time response systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Naini Jain: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Deepak Kumar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Kirti Bhardwaj:** Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Rupendra K. Sharma:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Jakub Holovsky:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Meena Mishra:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Conceptualization. **Yogendra Kumar Mishra:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sanjeev K. Sharma:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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